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Mass test and treat as an accelerator strategy for malaria elimination: a systematic review

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Mass test and treat as an accelerator strategy for malaria elimination: a systematic review

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Summary of findings table

Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) compared to no MTAT for reducing malaria transmission

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with no MTAT	Risk with mass testing and treatment (MTAT)				
Incidence of malaria infection (community level) assessed with: RDT & microscopy follow-up: 0-12 months	237 per 1,000	220 per 1,000 (204 to 239)	RR 0.93 (0.86 to 1.01)	275424 (2 RCTs) ^{1,2}	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) does not reduce incidence of malaria infection (community level).
Incidence of malaria infection (community level) assessed with: RDT/Microscopy/PCR follow-up: range 6 months to 12 months	4 per 1,000	5 per 1,000 (2 to 12)	RR 1.27 (0.51 to 3.14)	2349 (2 RCTs) ^{3,4,a}	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^b	Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) likely results in little to no difference in incidence of malaria infection (community level).
Prevalence of infection (community level) assessed with: Microscopy follow-up: 2 months	377 per 1,000	351 per 1,000 (309 to 392)	RR 0.93 (0.82 to 1.04)	3660 (1 RCT) ^{5,c}	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) does not reduce prevalence of infection.

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Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the transmission season) - not reported	-	-	-	-	-	
Incidence of clinical malaria (community level) assessed with: RDT/Microscopy follow-up: 0-12 months	316 per 1,000	218 per 1,000 (190 to 256)	RR 0.69 (0.60 to 0.81)	332454 (2 RCTs) ^{1,2}	⊕⊕⊕⊕ High	Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) reduces incidence of clinical malaria slightly.
Drug Resistance markers (community level) - not reported	-	-	-	-	-	
Adverse event (group targeted by the intervention)	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	6373 (1 RCT) ³	⊕○○○ Very low ^{d,e}	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment (MTAT) on adverse event (group targeted by the intervention).
Adverse event (group targeted by the intervention)	most common AEs during treatment were fever (0.023/person-day), headache (0.008/person-day), vomiting (0.006/person-day), cough (0.004/person-day), shivering (0.003/person-day), and nasal congestion (0.002/person-day)			(1 RCT) ⁴	⊕○○○ Very low ^f	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment (MTAT) on adverse event (group targeted by the intervention).
Serious Adverse event (group targeted by the intervention) (SAE)	0 per 1,000	0 per 1,000 (0 to 0)	not estimable	6373 (1 RCT) ³	⊕○○○ Very low ^{d,e}	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment (MTAT) on serious Adverse event (group targeted by the intervention).
Prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention) assessed with: RDT follow-up: 6 months	440 per 1,000	270 per 1,000 (159 to 415)	OR 0.47 (0.24 to 0.90)	1024 (1 RCT) ¹	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^g	Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) likely reduces prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention).

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Prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention) assessed with: PCR follow-up: 10 weeks	194 per 1,000	141 per 1,000 (108 to 183)	OR 0.68 (0.50 to 0.93)	875 (1 RCT) ^{4,h}	⊕⊕○○ Low ⁱ	Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) may result in a large reduction in prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention).
Prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention) assessed with: RDT	Three rounds of MTaT were conducted to determine prevalence in the asymptomatic reservoir. MTaT was compared with detection through passive surveillance prevalence. 1st round-moderate to high burden areas -50/28,527 i.e. 0.18% vs 0.06% from passive surveillance;2nd round-low to high burden areas - 7/11,363 i.e. 0.06% vs 0.03% from passive surveillance;3rd round- RCD of cryptic cases in 50 households -3/8,467 i.e. 0.03%			(1 observational study) ⁶	⊕○○○ Very low ⁱ	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment (MTAT) on prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention).
Prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention) assessed with: RDT/Microscopy follow-up: 9 months	378 per 1,000	344 per 1,000 (309 to 383)	RR 0.9104 (0.8183 to 1.0129)	2838 (1 RCT) ³	⊕⊕⊕○ Moderate ^g	Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) likely does not reduce prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention).
Prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention) (Prevalence of symptomatic malaria) assessed with: RDT follow-up: 2 months	34 per 1,000	1 per 1,000 (1 to 2)	OR 0.03 (0.02 to 0.07)	8508 (1 observational study) ^{7,k}	⊕○○○ Very low ⁱ	Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) may reduce/have little to no effect on prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention) but the evidence is very uncertain.
Prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention) (Prevalence of symptomatic parasitemia) assessed with: RDT follow-up: 1 years	438 per 1,000	415 per 1,000 (343 to 519)	OR 0.91 (0.67 to 1.38)	416 (1 observational study) ⁸	⊕○○○ Very low ⁱ	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment (MTAT) on prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention).

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Prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention) (Prevalence of asymptomatic parasitemia) assessed with: RDT follow-up: 1 years	363 per 1,000	302 per 1,000 (277 to 327)	OR 0.76 (0.67 to 0.85)	8907 (1 observational study) ^g	⊕○○○ Very low ^{g,i}	Mass testing and treatment (MTAT) may reduce/have little to no effect on prevalence of infection (group targeted by the intervention) but the evidence is very uncertain.
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*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the **relative effect** of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: confidence interval; OR: odds ratio; RR: risk ratio

Explanations

- a. One study has two intervention arms. Both intervention arms are pooled with another study and compared with the control. Control arm is inflated in value because it's the same comparison group for the two different intervention arm in one study.
- b. Used as a proxy for incidence of infection at the community level
- c. one study with 2 cohorts (year 1 & 2). pooled for both the cohorts
- d. SAEs and AEs are not classified based on intervention and control arms
- e. Unable to calculate control measures in absence of control measure
- f. Common AEs are reported for the whole study, however no break-up is provided for different arms
- g. Used as a proxy for prevalence of infection at the community level
- h. This cRCT have not assessed prevalence in no MTaT arm, instead prevalence has been assessed in MTaT3 vs MTaT2 arms
- i. There is clear evidence that outcome was measured in multiple eligible ways, but data for only subset of measure is fully reported, and the fully reported result is likely to have been selected on the basis of results
- j. Critical overall risk of bias due to inherent biases associated with study design
- k. Fever and symptoms screening before testing
- l. Study did not control for one confounding domain and missing register from health facility in intervention village - the analysis is unlikely to have removed the risk of bias arising from the missing data

Introduction

Rationale

Malaria and Global burden

Malaria is a preventable, diagnosable and treatable infectious disease; however, estimates show that there were 229 million malaria cases and 409 000 people died from the disease in 2019(1). The largest burden of malaria is in WHO Africa region, which accounts for 94% of malaria cases and 94% of deaths(1). Children under 5 and pregnant women are disproportionately affected by malaria. Around 11.6 million pregnant women were infected with malaria in moderate to high transmission countries in the WHO African region during 2019 which resulted in 822 000 low birth weight children(1). It is estimated that 274 000 children under the age of 5 died from malaria in 2019(1).

Elimination Strategy

A malaria-free world has been an ultimate goal embraced by the WHO, however the path to elimination requires continuous effort. The rate of progress towards this goal differs for each country and even within the country depending on various factors including biological determinants, level of investment, and availability of health services(2). Various preventive, diagnostic and treatment strategies recommended by the WHO have helped in control of disease in many endemic countries between 2000 and 2015 that has resulted in malaria elimination from 21 countries, and malaria free certification of 11 countries(3). The World Health Assembly, with aspirations of eradicating malaria, published the WHO Global Technical Strategy for malaria (GTS) in 2015. Some novel and fundamental principles are articulated in the GTS including that any malaria endemic country can aim for elimination of malaria transmission, regardless of malaria transmission level(2). The WHO has described three main strategic goals for countries to achieve malaria elimination: a) accelerate the decline in malaria transmission with the support of intensive surveillance; b) target specific high-risk groups that may not be reached through routine prevention and treatment services; and c) respond to individual cases to interrupt transmission. The concept of 'accelerator strategies' was defined as "timely, efficient interventions that rapidly reduce transmission intensity to sufficiently low levels that the few remaining infections can be found, treated and cleared as soon as they arise"(4). Mass testing and treatment is postulated to be such an accelerator strategy(3).

Description of intervention assessed

Mass testing and treatment (MTaT) is defined as "testing an entire population and treating individuals with a positive test result"(5). In the literature there is some variability in the terms used, for example, some studies use the word 'screen' to describe parasitological testing. Additionally, some MTA studies include a symptom screening step (e.g., for fever) before parasitological testing; sometimes this is for documentation only and sometimes the presence of fever is an indicator to do a parasitological test.

In the past, the focus of the global malaria community remained mainly on symptomatic cases. However, after realizing that asymptomatic malaria cases can carry the infection for years and their blood meals can transmit infection even during dry seasons, the interest towards dealing with asymptomatic infections is

growing(6). This interest is mainly due to the impact these cases can have on elimination. One strategy that targets asymptomatic cases and reduces the transmission is MTaT(3).

Since MTAT strategies target the entire population within a defined geographical area, it may be able to significantly reduce human malaria transmission across the whole community more rapidly than the standard of care.

Why it is important to do this review

In 2015, the WHO convened an evidence review group to examine the evidence of mass drug administration, mass screening and treatment, and focal screening and treatment for malaria(7). The objective was to examine the evidence that these strategies could interrupt malaria transmission.

Regarding MTaT, the evidence review group convened stated that “MTaT, MSaT achieved modest reductions in malaria transmission in mainland and island settings with low-to-moderate transmission but did not result in elimination”. These findings were submitted to the WHO Malaria Policy Advisory Committee, which concluded that mass screening and treatment for malaria (or MTaT) is not recommended to interrupt malaria transmission(8).

In summary, MTaT is not recommended as a strategy to interrupt malaria transmission. It is postulated, however, that it could be an effective strategy to reduce transmission and since 2015 a number of studies examining MTaT strategies have been conducted. Until now, the evidence regarding the impact on reducing malaria transmission has not been systematically assessed. This systematic review collected and examined all the available evidence to assess the benefits and harms of mass testing and treatment compared to no mass testing and treatment.

Objectives

The primary goal of this work was to carry out a comprehensive and updated systematic review of all available evidence regarding mass testing and treatment, to assess the relative effects (benefits and harms) of this accelerator strategy when applied to people residing in delimited geographical areas on human malaria transmission reduction, compared to no mass testing and treatment.

The specific objectives of this review were:

- To determine the benefits and harms of mass testing adults and children residing in delimited geographic area with ongoing transmission or malariogenic potential at the same time and treating confirmed cases with a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine including radical treatment for *P. vivax*, compared to no mass testing and treatment.
- to identify contextual factors including values and preferences, health equity, acceptability, feasibility and resources
- To determine which factors that may modify epidemiologically the effect of mass testing and treatment (potential effect modifiers¹).

Ultimately, this systematic review was conducted to provide evidence to support the development of recommendations related to the activities around mass testing and treatment that countries should undertake to work towards achieving elimination, beyond case management and vector control.

Table 1. displays the details of the population, intervention, comparison and outcomes of the review question.

Table 1. PICO descriptors for Mass Testing and Treatment	
Review question: <i>Should people residing in delimited geographic areas be tested for malaria at the same time and treated if positive to reduce human malaria transmission?</i>	
Setting	An area with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential
Population	Adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area
Intervention	Parasitologic testing of the entire population and treatment of confirmed cases at approximately the same time
Comparison	No intervention
Outcomes (in priority order)	Community level <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incidence of malaria infection 2. Prevalence of malaria infection 3. Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the transmission season) 4. Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases 5. Drug resistance markers Among the group targeted by the intervention:

¹ The potential effect modifiers for MTaT are: level of transmission, vector control coverage, malaria parasite species, antimalarial medication, screening before testing, limit of detection and sensitivity of the parasitological test.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adverse events 2. Prevalence of infection² 3. Drug resistance markers
Timeframe	Up to 36 months after the last round

Methods

Eligibility criteria

The study and report characteristics that were used as criteria for eligibility in this review are described below.

Types of setting

Studies conducted in any area with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential were included.

Types of study designs

Following study designs were included in the review

- Randomized study designs
 - Cluster-randomized controlled trials with at least two clusters per arm.
 - Cluster-randomized crossover trials with at least two clusters per arm.
 - Cluster-randomized stepped wedge designs with at least four clusters.
 - Cluster-randomized factorial designs with at least two clusters per level.
- Non-randomized study designs
 - Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials with at least two clusters per arm.
 - Controlled before and after studies with at least two sites per arm and a contemporaneous control group.
 - Interrupted time series (controlled or not) where the intervention occurs at a defined point in time and there were at least three data points collected over one year pre-intervention and three data points collected one-year post-intervention.
 - Uncontrolled before and after studies and before and after studies with historical controls³

² Used as an intermediate outcome for prevalence of malaria infection at the community level.

³ These studies were judged to have a critical risk of bias

Studies were excluded if:

- Follow-up periods for intervention and control groups were not the same, or timing of baseline and endline surveys were not same in intervention and control arms.
- Background interventions were not equally implemented between intervention and control arms (i.e., the same set of co-interventions were not available in both arms) or were implemented at different times.

Types of participants

Adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area with ongoing human malaria transmission or malariogenic potential were included (malariogenic potential meaning that although there were no active cases of malaria and no transmission, the environmental conditions were such that malaria transmission could occur in the geographical area). Studies targeting participants with particular characteristics (e.g., high risk groups) were excluded.

Types of interventions

Intervention arm

For the purpose of this review, mass testing and treatment was defined as parasitologic testing of the entire population and treatment of confirmed cases at approximately the same time. Only studies which tested population at the same time and treated cases at approximately the same time were included(3).

Studies that include a screening step for the purpose of collecting information were included. Studies that include a screening step as a means to target the use of parasitological testing were also included for subgroup analysis.

Control arm

The comparison arms considered for this review were no MTaT intervention or the current standard of care.

Background interventions

We anticipated that existing control efforts would include background interventions that provide adequate access to case management, testing and treatment for the populations within an intervention area. We documented the standard of care for the place at that time. Similarly, for studies in areas that have individual-level chemoprevention strategies as part of their standard of care, we documented the details on time and duration of these interventions, where available. Furthermore, background interventions including the level of vector control coverage were also recorded.

Exclusion criteria

This review was focused on mass testing and treatment and did not assess or evaluate the efficacy of antimalarial, drug regimens/ dosing, or diagnostic tests. Likewise, the supply chain, resource management, access to care, and quality of care were also excluded. While we are aware that these all

play a significant role in overall intervention effectiveness, we did not individually assess these program characteristics.

Outcomes

Studies with at least one of the following were included: one or more outcomes, data on contextual factors, or mathematical modelling results. For outcomes that specified parasitological confirmation, the possible diagnostic approaches included malaria rapid diagnostic tests (RDT), microscopy, or molecular methods such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

The following outcomes were assessed:

- incidence of infection at the community level
- prevalence of infection at the community level
- elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the transmission season)
- incidence of clinical malaria
- drug resistance markers
- adverse events among the group targeted by the intervention⁴
- prevalence among the group targeted by the intervention⁵

Timing of outcome measurements

The pre-intervention of baseline period was defined as 1-12 months prior to the first round of mass testing and treatment. The post-intervention period refers to the time period following the last round of mass testing and treatment.

Time of follow-up

Studies with all follow-up periods were included; however, we only extracted data on follow-up periods from 1-24 months after the last round of mass testing and treatment. We contacted the lead researchers if data was not reported in this timeframe.

Contextual factors

For the assessment of the evidence of contextual factors relevant to implementation and operational aspects of the intervention, all study designs, including qualitative studies were included.

⁴ Meant to be distinguished from the community-level outcomes, but refers not only in the study arm that got the intervention, but both intervention and control arms.

⁵ Although the PICO question referred to “transmission”, which is a community-level outcome, it was decided to include prevalence among the group targeted by the intervention as a proxy indicator of the potential effect at the community level. Finding no effect of the intervention among the targeted group would be a reliable proxy for no effect on community transmission. However, a positive effect among the targeted group would not be a reliable proxy for the effect on community transmission.

The following contextual factors were assessed:

- a. Values and preferences – The values and preferences of the individuals and populations affected by the recommendation with respect to the outcomes associated with the intervention;
- b. Acceptability - extent to which those benefiting from an intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the intervention to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention;
- c. Health equity– extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, SES status, residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all;
- d. Resource use – cost, overall economic impact, cost-benefit; and,
- e. Feasibility– legal barriers to implementation, interaction with existing health system, need for and use of the existing health workforce.

Mathematical modelling studies

Modeling studies were used to provide evidence for operational considerations, such as timing of the intervention, coverage rates, number of rounds, etc. These studies were further categorized as:

- simulation mathematical studies based on assumptions
- mathematical modelling studies grounded in empirical data from specific study sites

Information sources

The studies included in this review were identified by searching the indexed and the grey literature without timeframe limitations. Pre-defined search terms and relevant subheadings, as well as keywords related to malaria, antimalarials, and mass testing and treatment were used.

The following sources were systematically searched(3):

- Bibliographic databases: Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register (CIDG SR); Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL); MEDLINE (Pubmed); EMBASE (Ovid); CAB Abstracts (Web of Science); and LILACS.
- Other databases: The Archives of the World Health Organization; US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (clinicaltrials.gov); ISRCTN registry; The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP) and the MESA Track database.
- Conference proceedings: American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) Annual Meetings, Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health Future of malaria research

Symposium, Keystone/MESA Symposium, Women in Malaria Conference, Doctors Without Borders (MSF) Scientific Days 2021, Asia Pacific Malaria Elimination Network (APMEN) Journal Clubs (TechTalks), 6th Southern Africa Malaria Research Conference.

- The bibliographies in the included studies were searched for further studies.
- Malaria researchers and organizations were asked for inputs regarding relevant published and unpublished studies.
- If studies were identified that were unpublished, the lead researcher were contacted regarding plans to publish the work. Researchers were asked to respond within four weeks. No studies which were not in the public domain were included in this review.

Search strategy

A preliminary search of literature indexed in PubMed was conducted in August 2020 to help refine the keywords and MeSH terms to further understand the state of the literature on malaria elimination and MTaT. This scoping search strategy was developed in consultation with a librarian from the University of Barcelona.

The final search strategy for the review was developed in collaboration with a systematic review information specialist and was conducted in March 2021 based on the finalized PICO question. The final search strategy is detailed in **Appendix 1**.

Data management

Records and data throughout the review were managed using the software system Mendeley⁶ for storage of identified articles. Study details and data points were recorded in an excel spreadsheet and were shared between the systematic review authors using G-suite tools. When not already indexed in the database, information on the included studies were also entered in the malaria eradication scientific alliance (MESA) tracking tool (MESA Track⁷) as a “deep dive” to allow for future reference of projects that may generate relevant results for the future guidelines recommendations. EppiReviewer 4.0 and EppiReviewer⁸ web were used for title/abstract, full-text screening, recording outcome data and meta-analysis.

⁶ Mendeley is a company based in London, UK, which provides products and services for academic researchers. It is most known for its reference manager which is used to manage and share research papers and generate bibliographies for scholarly articles. Website: www.mendeley.com

⁷ MESA Track is a living database which captures research projects and institutions’ portfolios in malaria elimination and eradication. The tool was developed and managed by the MESA Alliance, hosted at the Barcelona Institute for Global Health and funded by a grant from the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation. Website: mesamalaria.org/mesa-track

⁸ Eppi-reviewer is an application for literature reviews, including systematic reviews, meta-analysis, ‘narrative’ reviews and meta-ethnographies. The tool was developed and maintained by the EPPI-Centre at the Social Science Research Unit of the UCL Institute of Education, University of London, UK. Website: eppi.ioe.ac.uk. Eppi-Reviewer was last updated on 15 October 2020 (version 4.11.5.1).

Selection process

Two or three authors independently identified studies for inclusion or exclusion. In the first round of selection, the primary author and the secondary author independently assessed titles and abstracts of all the articles retrieved from the search strategy and excluded irrelevant articles. In case of discrepancies a third author was consulted. In the second round of selection, the primary author and two secondary authors independently assessed the full-text articles of all studies identified as potentially eligible and those which satisfied the criteria were retained for inclusion. A third author for full-text screening was included due to large number of studies identified from title/abstract screening. For any discrepancies or disagreements in inclusion by the authors, the remaining systematic review team members assessed the study for inclusion. In the event that there was still disagreement, the WHO methodologist and Elimination Guidelines Development team lead were consulted for final determination. The abstract/title screening process and full-text review processes were tested in a calibration exercise with the study authors using the EPPI Reviewer 4.0 and/or Eppi Reviewer Web tool. Each author practiced the abstract/title screening and full-text review independently, followed by development of a written standard operating procedure (SOP) to codify the screening process. The authors then conducted an exercise to compare the screening outcomes for the abstract/ title and full text review on a subset of articles using the corresponding SOPs in the EPPI Reviewer tool. The final list of studies included in the full-text review was shared with the GDG, WHO methodologist and malaria elimination team lead for agreement

After data extraction and categorization of study information, the included articles were assessed for meta-analysis, narrative or contextual contribution to the review by the primary author with confirmation by a second review team member. Outcome data and time points for the intervention and follow-up timeframe determined the potential for meta-analyses. Figure i and Figure ii in Appendix 2 represent the flow diagram for the review methodology and the adapted PRISMA flow diagram for study synthesis and meta-analysis.

Data collection process

The primary and secondary authors independently extracted data from the included studies. Later the extracted data were compared for the confirmation. In order to clarify or obtain any information that was lacking or not clearly described in the published article, the study authors were contacted and asked to share further information within a four week period. For data that could not be retrieved, the missing data was not added by imputation methods, rather the study was excluded from specific quantitative analyses and a qualitative summary was completed.

Data items

Where possible, the data extracted from the studies included both descriptive data and study calculations and measurements (where relevant) to assess comparability and eligibility for data synthesis and pooled analyses. Variables for data extraction included: study design, setting, demographics, methodology, treatment, comparison, time period, baseline characteristics, intervention, outcomes, study biases,

background interventions, and any other contextual study information that was informative in assessing confidence as evidence. The data extraction form was developed by the review author to capture the necessary study variables and was practiced for the data collection process. **Table i in Appendix 2** provides further details for all the variables for which data were needed.

Study risk of bias assessment

Two authors independently assessed the risk of bias of each of the included studies and the outcome measures reported therein. A comparison was performed at the domain level for agreement.

Various tools were used to assess the risk of bias based on the study design(3):

- For randomized controlled trials, the Cochrane risk of bias (RoB2) tool was used (9), as well as the five additional criteria in Section 23.1.2 of the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions that relate specifically to RCTs(10), with an assessment reported as low risk, some concern, high-risk or unclear. This RoB assessment was conducted at the outcome level. The results displayed as summary graphs.
- For non-randomized controlled trials and intermittent time series studies, the ROBINS-I tool from the Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC) Group(11) was used with an assessment reported as low risk, moderate risk, serious risk, critical risk, or no information. If any domain assessed reached a critical risk of bias, the assessment was discontinued, as further evaluation would have not influenced how the certainty of the evidence was assessed.
- Uncontrolled before-and-after studies and after studies and before and after studies with historical controls were judged to have a critical risk of bias(3). These studies were only included if there were no other studies available or if there were no other studies for an important subgroup or sensitivity analyses.

For studies which were assessed to have critical risk of bias, a descriptive analysis and report with the study findings and any reported effect estimates were generated(3).

The risk of bias assessments were conducted using predefined criteria for Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) as described in the Certainty Assessment section below. Any disagreements or discrepancies between reviewers were resolved through discussion or by consulting a third author. If a consensus was not reached, the systematic review team was consulted the WHO methodologist(3).

Effect measures

Synthesis methods

The study intervention characteristics were tabulated and compared for each outcome to decide the study eligibility for synthesis. Meta-analysis was carried out to derive pooled estimates of effect for each outcome of interest for data where quantitative synthesis was doable.

For dichotomous outcomes (e.g., infection, adverse events, etc.) from randomized studies, we extracted the crude number of cases, number of participants targeted in the intervention, those reporting adverse events, and the total number of participants assessed for the outcome in each study arm. For each outcome the crude proportions or ratios were recorded, as well as the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm for incidence rates. Measures of variance (e.g., standard error, intercorrelation coefficient or coefficient of variance) were included if provided in the study methods. We recorded both crude and adjusted measures of effect (e.g., risk ratio (RR), odds ratio (OR), rate ratio (RR), or mean difference (MD)) with 95% confidence intervals (CI). For non-randomized studies, we extracted adjusted measures of intervention effects that attempted to control for confounding including RRs and/or rate ratios.

Unit of analysis

For cRCTs, measures of effect adjusted for clustering were used if available. The raw data was adjusted using the intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC) values and mean cluster size obtained from the study or authors, and where unavailable, it was extrapolated from similar studies. For studies that reported an adjusted effect estimate, the adjusted value was used and the standard error was calculated and entered into Eppi-Reviewer without further analysis. If studies had more than one intervention arms, treatment arms were combined if appropriate in the meta-analysis

Data synthesis

Data from randomized studies and non-randomized studies were pooled for meta-analysis separately. Studies were analyzed using meta-analysis using a fixed-effect model.

Assessment of heterogeneity

Statistical heterogeneity was tested using the chi-squared (χ^2), statistic test for study effect measures (P-value <0.05 as significant) and the degree of inconsistency (I^2), statistic to test whether the variation across studies that was due to heterogeneity rather than chance. We interpreted the inconsistency across study outcomes effect measures according to a scale of very low, low, moderate, or high with values of <25%, 26 - 50%, 51 – 74% and >75%(12). We did not perform meta-analysis, if high levels of heterogeneity among the studies existed ($I^2 \geq 50\%$) and inconsistency was found in the direction of the effect with non-overlapping CIs. In such cases, the study design and characteristics in the included studies were analyzed by subgroup analysis or sensitivity analysis.

Sub group analysis

For the prioritized potential effect modifiers, data were to be stratified for a subgroup analysis if there were at least 2 studies per stratum. The a priori subgroups to be assessed were:

- Use of symptom screening before testing
- Transmission level
- Location of community (geographically isolated)

- Antimalarial medication used, short-acting vs long-acting

If quantitative synthesis were not appropriate due to limited number of studies and inability to reduce substantial heterogeneity, the subgroup analysis was not performed, and the resultant data were summarized based on key findings in a narrative description. Likewise, for the contextual factors, data were stratified by categories described above and textually summarized.

Reporting bias assessment

Most reporting biases are accounted for within the approach used for identification of studies for the review. Meta-biases such as selective reporting of bias were assessed in part by the RoB assessments being conducted at the study-level and in the data extraction process, which allowed for identification of gaps in reported outcomes across studies. For within study selective reporting bias for included randomized studies, if a trial registration was available, the registration was checked for consistency in methodology, outcomes planned and what was reported in the study. For publication bias, funnel plots were planned to be generated if there were at least 10 studies included in the analysis.

Certainty assessment

The GRADE method was used to assess the certainty of evidence for each intervention across each outcome measure (**Table 2**). Randomized studies were initially ranked as having high certainty of evidence and non-randomized studies were initially ranked as having low certainty. If there was evidence of risk of bias, imprecision, inconsistency of evidence, indirectness, or publication bias, the level of certainty was downgraded by one level for each of these factors. For non-randomized studies, if there was evidence of large magnitude of effect, evidence of a dose-response relationship, or where it was likely that residual confounding would increase the magnitude of effect the level of certainty was upgraded by one level for each of these factors.

Table 2. GRADE Criteria

Certainty	Interpretation
Very Low	The true effect is markedly different from the estimated effect
Low	The true effect might be markedly different from the estimated effect
Moderate	The authors believe that the true effect is probably close to the estimated effect
High	The authors have a lot of confidence that the true effect is similar to the estimated effect

To ensure consistency in judgements around precision and size of absolute effect measures of interventions to reduce transmission, thresholds for determining public health value of interventions were determined as listed in **Table 3**:

Table 3. Categorization of effect sizes

Species and transmission level	Effect size	Absolute difference in prevalence	Absolute difference in annual incidence
<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> – Very low to low	Little to no	0 to 0.03% (0-0.3 per 1000)	0 to 3 per 1000 person-year
	Slight or some (public health value threshold)	0.04% to 0.1% (0.4 to 1 per 1000)	4 to 10 per 1000 person-year
	Large	>0.1% (>1 per 1000)	> 10 per 1000 person-year
<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> – Moderate to high	Little to no	0 to 10% (0 to 100 per 1000)	0 to 250 per 1000 person-year
	Slight or some (public health value threshold)	10 to 20% (100 to 200 per 1000)	250 to 333 per 1000 person-year
	Large	>20% (>200 per 1000)	>333 per 1000 person-year
<i>Plasmodium vivax</i>	Little to no	0 to 5% (0 to 50 per 1000)	0 to 125 per 1000 person-year
	Slight or some (public health value threshold)	5% to 10% (50 to 100 per 1000)	125 to 250 per 1000 person-year
	Large	>10% (>100)	>250 per 1000 person-year

For the summary of findings statements, we considered both the size of the effect and the certainty of evidence assessments (Table 4)(13).

Table 4. Summary of findings statements criteria

Effect size	Certainty			
	High	Moderate	Low	Very low
Large	MTaT results in a large reduction/increase in outcome	MTaT likely/probably results in a large reduction/increase in outcome	MTaT may result in a large reduction/increase in outcome	The evidence is very uncertain about the effect of MTaT on outcome MTaT may reduce/increase/have little to no effect on outcome but the evidence is very uncertain
Moderate	MTaT reduces/increases outcome MTaT results in a reduction/increase in outcome	MTaT likely/probably results in a large reduction/increase in outcome	MTaT may reduce/increase outcome	
Small but important	MTaT reduces/increases outcome slightly	MTaT probably/likely results in a slight reduction/increase in outcome	MTaT may result in a slight reduction/increase in outcome	
Trivial, small, unimportant or no effect	MTaT results in little to no difference in outcome	MTaT likely/probably results in little to no difference in outcome	MTaT may result in little to no difference in outcome	

MTaT: Mass Testing and Treatment

Review of GRADE summary of findings tables and criteria was conducted by the WHO methodologist and malaria elimination team lead for agreement.

For the contextual factors assessed in the review, we planned to use the 'Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative research' (GRADE-CERQual) approach. The GRADE-CERQual approach provides a certainty or confidence of a qualitative syntheses of studies using the following four components: 1) the methodological limitations, 2) coherence, 3) the adequacy of data supporting a review finding, and 4) the relevance of data from primary studies(13)Each contextual factor was planned to be assessed and interpreted using the criteria adapted from the descriptive interpretations by Lewin et.al(14). However, given the low number of studies included for contextual factors and the fact that no synthesis for contextual factors was possible, it was decided to only produce textual summaries of findings for each study.

Results

Study selection

A total of 4139 records were identified: 4059 via searching databases, 40 from registers, and 40 via other methods (e.g., websites, organizations and citation searching). Before the screening, 1295 records were removed due to duplication, with a total of 2844 records to be screened against title and abstract eligibility (2804 identified via databases and registers and 40 identified via other methods). Of these, 100 were assessed using the full-text eligibility criteria. After the full-text screening, seven studies were included for assessment of outcome data (eight reports), three studies were included for assessment of contextual factors (5 reports), and ten studies were included for mathematical modelling. The detailed Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Flow Diagram is presented in **Appendix 3**, which also includes the reasons for exclusion.

Three studies appeared to meet the inclusion criteria but were excluded because they were still in progress with no published results (See [Ongoing studies](#)).

Study characteristics

Included and excluded studies are described in detail in the [Characteristics of studies tables](#).

Included studies

Seven studies met criteria for inclusion: four cRCTs, conducted in Kenya (**Samuels 2020**(15) and **Desai 2020**(16)), Indonesia (**Sutanto 2018**(17)), Zambia (**Larsen 2015**(18)) and Burkina Faso (**Tiono 2013**(19)); one quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trial conducted in Senegal (**Linn 2015**(20)); and one uncontrolled before and after study conducted in Ghana (**Ndong 2019**(21)) and India (**Bharti 2020**(22)). Additionally, five articles were assessed for contextual factors: two articles for acceptability (**Shuford 2016**(23)) and (**Silumbe 2015**(24)); one article for resource use (**Silumbe 2015**(25)) and two articles for feasibility (**Odero 2019**(26)) and (**Ndong 2019**(27)). Also, ten mathematical modelling studies were

included in this review, all categorized under the simulation category: 1) **Sallah 2020**(28); 2) **Millar 2020**(29); 3) **Stuckey 2016**(30); 4) **Nikolov 2016**(31); 5) **Gerardin 2016**(32); 6) **Slater 2015**(33); 7) **Rosas-Aguirre 2015**(34); 8) **Gerardin 2015**(35); 9) **Crowell 2013**(36); and 10) **Kern 2011**(37).

Descriptive characteristics of the seven included studies are summarized in **Table 3** and described in detail in the [Characteristics of included studies tables](#).

Interventions

Samuels 2020(15) and **Desai 2020**(16) reported on a cRCT that took place in Siaya county, western Kenya, from 2013 to 2015. Six rounds of community-based intermittent mass testing and treatment using rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) and dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) were deployed over the period of two years (three rounds per year), targeting all residents living in villages around 10 health facility catchment areas. **Sutanto 2018**(17), reported on a cRCT conducted in Wesiku district, West Timor, Indonesia in 2013. This three-arm study deployed two intervention arms with two (MST2) and three (MST3) rounds of mass screening and treatment where MST3 was implemented monthly from June to August with 5 week intervals, whereas two rounds of MST2 were implemented with 10 weeks interval. All residents living in the selected villages and hamlets were tested with a microscopic assessment and polymerase chain reaction (PCR) examinations and all microscopy positive subjects were treated with DHP or primaquine. **Larsen 2015**(18) reported on a community randomized step-wedge control trial (SW-CRT) that deployed population-wide malaria testing and treatment with RDTs and artemether-lumefantrine (AL) in 2012-2013. Three MTaT rounds were conducted in dry season of 2012 in Gwebme, Siavonga, Sinazongwe and Kalomo districts along Lake Kariba in Southern province, Zambia. **Tiono 2013**(19) published a cRCT that was conducted in Saponé district, Burkina Faso. Three community-wide screening and treatment campaigns, approximately 1 month apart between January and April 2011, tested all inhabitants of selected villages with RDTs and treated positive individuals with AL.

Linn 2015(20) described a quasi-experimental study in Saraya health district in the region of Kedougou, Senegal that deployed a ProACT model, whereby home care providers in all selected villages went door to door to every household and checked for symptomatic malaria cases, testing with RDTs, and administering ACT to positive individuals. These sweeps were conducted weekly from July to November 2013. The uncontrolled before and after study reported by **Ndong 2019**(21), deployed mass testing, treatment, and tracking (MTTT) in Pakro sub-district, Ghana from 2017-2018. Three rounds of MTTT were implemented four months apart, testing the entire population with RDTs and treating positive cases with ACTs. **Bharti 2020**(22) was a project-based uncontrolled before and after study that deployed integrated malaria control interventions including LLINS, IRS, active case detection and mass screening and treatment (MSAT) to reduce malaria burden in Mandla, Madhya Pradesh, India between 2017-2020. Three rounds of MSAT were conducted in different annual parasitic incidence (API) settings.

Outcomes

Incidence of malaria infection at the community level were reported in three cRCTs and one SW-cRCT. **Desai 2020**(16) followed two randomly selected cohorts of residents (one each year) through monthly scheduled visits and unscheduled sick visits from June (baseline) to May. Incidence of malaria infection

was measured by RDT and microscopy. **Larsen 2018(18)**, reported HMIS-based confirmed outpatient cases collected monthly for whole year measured by RDTs. **Sutanto 2018(17)** followed a cohort of school children for 6 months from the first round of the intervention and incidence was measured by microscopy and PCR. Likewise, **Tiono 2013(19)** also followed infant and children <59 months for whole year from the start of the intervention. Incidence of infection was measured by RDTs.

Prevalence of infection at the community level was reported in cRCT **Samuels 2020(15)** at 2 months post-intervention. The intervention was delivered from September 2013 to April 2014 (three rounds) and September 2014 to April 2015 (three rounds); population based cross-sectional surveys were conducted in July prior to inception of intervention (baseline) and in July each year after the completion of third round. Prevalence was measured by RDT and microscopy.

Incidence of clinical malaria were reported in two cRCTs **Desai 2020(16)** and **Larsen 2018(18)**. Incidence of clinical malaria was collected from health facilities weekly or monthly after the first rounds of MTaT for the whole year.

Serious adverse events (SAEs) were reported in one cRCT **Tiono 2013(19)** monitored from the time of the consent until 30 days after the subject has stopped study participation. Adverse events (AEs) were reported in two cRCTs i.e., **Tiono 2013(19)** collected during a period of 7 days from treatment administration, whereas **Sutanto 2018(17)**, reported AEs monitored by staff at community level and teachers at school level.

Prevalence of infection in the group targeted by the intervention was reported in two cRCTs, one SW-CRT, one quasi-experimental study and two uncontrolled before and after studies. **Sutanto 2018(17)** reported prevalence in two intervention arms i.e., mass screening and treatment with two (MST2) and three rounds (MST3). Prevalence in the MST2 arm was measured 10 weeks post-first round, whereas in MST3 it was measured 5 weeks post-second round using microscopy and PCR. **Larsen 2015(18)** measured prevalence using RDTs in children 1-59, 6 months post-intervention (after completion of third round). **Tiono 2013(19)**, measured prevalence of asymptomatic carrier, 9 months post-intervention (completion of third round), by using microscopy. The quasi-experimental study, **Linn 2015(20)** measured prevalence of infection in symptomatic subjects, sweeping all households for symptomatic cases weekly for 21 weeks. Prevalence was measured using RDTs. An uncontrolled before and after study, **Ndong 2019(21)**, reported prevalence of symptomatic and asymptomatic infection 4 months post-intervention (after completion of third round). Prevalence was measured using RDTs. **Bharti 2020(22)** measured prevalence of malaria infection in three different API settings i.e., first round in moderate to high API areas, second round in low to high API areas and third round was conducted in low API areas around cryptic cases. This study did not evaluate the impact of MSAT on disease burden, instead

Contextual factors

Perception of community about mass testing and treatment was assessed in two studies i.e., **Shuford 2016(23)**, based on the study reported in **Samuels 2020(15)** and **Desai 2020(16)**; and **Silumbe 2015(24)** based on the study reported in **Larsen 2015(18)**. Cost and cost-effectiveness of mass testing and treatment was assessed by **Silumbe 2015(25)** based on the study reported in **Larsen**

2015(18). Two studies reported feasibility of conducting mass testing and treatment i.e., **Odero 2019(26)** based on the study reported in **Samuels 2020(15)** and **Desai 2020(16)**; and **Ndong 2019(27)** based on the before and after study conducted by **Ndong 2019(21)**.

Excluded studies

Seventy nine articles were excluded after full-text screening due to the following reasons: incorrect intervention (n=10), incorrect population (n=1), incorrect study focus area (n=3), incorrect study design (n=5), cross-referenced article (n=7), not reported outcomes of interest (n=1), reports excluded for contextual factors (n=6), reports excluded for mathematical modelling (6) or because a full report could not be retrieved (e.g., abstract, protocol or other document and ongoing studies) (n=40). All full-text studies that did not meet eligibility criteria are listed with their reasons for exclusion in the [Characteristics of excluded studies table](#).

Table 5. Characteristics of included studies

Study	Location	Year(s)	Study design	Intervention	Outcomes reported
Samuels 2020(15) Desai 2020(16)	Siaya, Western Kenya	2013- 2015	cRCT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Target population: all inhabitants ● Intervention: MTaT ● Comparator: standard of care ● Drug: DP/AL/quinine ● Rounds: six, (three per year over two years) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incidence of malaria infection at the community level (cohort followed monthly throughout the year) ● Prevalence of infection at the community level (2 months post-intervention) ● Incidence of clinical malaria at the community level (follow-up range Sep 2013-Sep 2015)
Sutanto 2018(17)	Wesiku, West Timor, Indonesia	2013	cRCT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Target population: all inhabitants ● Intervention: MST ● Comparator: No MST ● Drug: DP/primaquine ● Rounds: three rounds every five weeks (MST3) Two rounds every 10 weeks (MST2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incidence of infection at the community level (followed monthly for six months) ● AEs ● Prevalence of infection among those targeted (5 weeks post second round-MST3) (10 weeks post first round-MST2)
Larsen 2015(18)	Southern Zambia	2012- 2013	SW- cRCT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Target population: all inhabitants ● Intervention: MTaT ● Comparator: standard of care ● Drug: AL ● Rounds: three 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incidence of malaria infection at the community level (monthly throughout the year) ● Incidence of clinical malaria at the community level (monthly throughout the year) ● Prevalence of infection among those targeted (6 months post-intervention))
Tiono 2013(19)	Saponé, Burkina Faso	2011- 2012	cRCT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Target population: all inhabitants ● Intervention: community wide screening and treatment ● Comparator: standard of care ● Drug: AL 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AEs reported within 7 days) ● SAEs (within 30 days of any treatment) ● Prevalence of infection among those targeted (9 months post-intervention)

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rounds: 3 rounds 	
Linn 2015(20)	Senegal	2013	Quasi-experi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Target population: every household ● Intervention: ProACT ● Comparator: standard of care ● Drug: ACT ● Rounds: weekly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prevalence of infection among those targeted (Week 21 of intervention)
Ndong 2019(21)	Pakro, Ghana	2017-2018	uBAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Target population: all inhabitants ● Intervention: MTTT ● Comparator: N/A ● Drug: AA/AL ● Rounds: three rounds every 4 months 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Prevalence of infection among those targeted (asymptomatic parasitemia-4 months post intervention) ● Prevalence of infection among those targeted (symptomatic parasitemia-4 months post intervention)
Bharti 2020(22)	Mandla, India	2017-2020	uBAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Targeted population: all inhabitants ● Intervention: ITN, IRS, active case management and Mass screening and treatment ● Comparator: N/A ● Drug: ACT ● Rounds: 3 rounds in different API areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Three rounds of MTaT were conducted to determine prevalence in the asymptomatic reservoir. MTaT was compared with detection through passive surveillance prevalence. 1st round-moderate to high burden areas - 50/28,527 i.e. 0.18% vs 0.06% from passive surveillance; 2nd round-low to high burden areas - 7/11,363 i.e. 0.06% vs 0.03% from passive surveillance; 3rd round- around cryptic cases in 50 households -3/8,467 i.e. 0.03%

AEs: adverse events; SAEs: serious adverse events; AL: artemether-lumefantrine; DP: dihydroartemisinin- piperazine; AA: artesunate-amodiaquine; AST: Artemisinin-based combination therapies; MST: mass screening and treatment; SAEs: serious adverse events; SP/AQ: sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine + amodiaquine; uBAF: uncontrolled before and after; API: annual parasitic incidence.

Risk of bias in studies

Detailed explanations for the judgements are provided in the [Characteristics of included studies tables](#).

cRCTs

Assessments for risk of bias for the outcomes assessed in the four cRCT (Larsen 2015(18), Samuels 2020(15), Desai 2020(16), Sutanto 2018(17) & Tiono 2013(19)) are summarized in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1. Risk of Bias summary for the outcomes assessed in the cRCTs.

D1a: randomization process; D1b: timing of identification or recruitment of participants; D2: deviations from the intended interventions; D3: missing outcome data; D4: measurement of the outcome; D5: selection of the reported result.

Study ID	Outcome	D1a	D1b	D2	D3	D4	D5	Overall
Larsen 2015	Incidence of infection community	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Larsen 2015	Incidence of clinical malaria community	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Larsen 2015	Prevalence targeted	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Samuels 2020	Prevalence community	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Desai 2020	Incidence of infection community	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Desai 2020	Incidence of clinical malaria community	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Sutanto 2018	Incidence of infection community	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Sutanto 2018	Prevalence targeted	+	+	+	+	+	-	-
Sutanto 2018	Adverse events	+	+	+	+	+	!	!
Tiono 2013	Incidence of infection community	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Tiono 2013	AEs including SAEs	+	+	+	+	+	!	!
Tiono 2013	Prevalence targeted	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Figure 2. Risk of Bias summary for the cRCTs by percentage.

Domain 1a: Randomization process

All studies were rated as low risk of bias in terms of the randomization process. It was considered that all studies used acceptable randomization processes; mostly restricted randomization **Samuel 2020(15)/Desai 2020(16)**, **Sutanto 2018(17)** and **Tiono 2013(19)**, or used satellite imagery from google earth to create the randomization group **Larsen 2015(18)**.

D1b: timing of identification or recruitment of participants

Risk of bias for recruitment of participants was rated as low for all outcomes.

D2: deviations from the intended interventions

It was considered that there were no notable deviations from the intended interventions in all outcomes assessed. Even though all studies were unblinded, there was nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.

D3: missing outcome data

For incidence of malaria infection (community level), prevalence of malaria (community level), incidence of clinical malaria (community level), adverse events including serious adverse events and prevalence of infection among targeted, all four studies were rated low risk.

D4: measurement of the outcome

For, incidence of malaria infection (community level), all four studies reporting these effects were rated low risk, as measurement of this outcome was done by staff either unaware of study group assignment or samples were analyzed by two independent microscopists or the outcome measurements were done by trained and skilled staff. Likewise, for prevalence of infection at community level, only one study reported this effect (**Samuels 2020(15)**), and the outcome assessors were blinded to study arms. Two studies (**Tiono 2013(19)** and **Sutanto 2018(17)**) reported incidence of clinical malaria at the community level, and both were rated low risk as the data was collected from the health facility on a weekly or monthly basis. AEs including SAEs were reported in two studies and both were rated low risk as adverse events were assessed by experienced personnel and it was unlikely that participants reported presence of adverse events due to awareness of the arm to which they were assigned. Prevalence of infection among the targeted was reported by all four studies and all were rated low risk, as measurement of this outcome was done by staff either unaware of study group assignment or samples were analyzed by two independent microscopist or the outcome measurement were done by trained and skilled staff.

D5: selection of the reported result

Risk of bias for selection of the reported result was rated low for all the studies that reported incidence of malaria infection (community level), prevalence of malaria infection (community level) and incidence of clinical malaria (community level) because the reported primary and secondary outcomes were the same as reported in clinicaltrials.gov or in-depth in their protocol. On the other hand, for prevalence of

infection among those targeted, all studies were rated low risk except for **Sutanto 2018**(17) as there was clear evidence that the measurement was analyzed in multiple eligible ways, but data of only a subset has been reported i.e., species specific analysis, thus it was rated high risk. For AEs and SAEs, both the studies that reported this effect were rated as having some concerns due to reporting of cumulative outcome (not separated for arms).

Quasi-experimental study

Figures 3 summarizes the risk of bias assessment for the quasi-experimental study **Linn 2015**(20)

Figure 3. Risk of Bias summary for the quasi-experimental study

D1: Bias due to confounding

Bias due to confounding was rated as serious because the potential confounding due to gold rush was not controlled due to unavailability of data.

D2: Bias due to selection of participants into the study

Bias due to selection of participants was rated as low because it was considered that all participants who would have been eligible for the trial were included in the study, and the start of follow up and start of intervention coincided for each participant.

D3: Bias in classification of interventions

It was considered that there was low risk of bias in classification of interventions, because there was nothing to suggest that the intervention status was not well defined and classified.

D4: Bias due to deviations from intended interventions

Bias due to deviation from intended intervention was rated as low because there was no evidence that suggest the deviation in intervention from planned intervention.

D5: Bias due to missing data

Bias due to missing data was rated moderate due to missing register from health facility in intervention village and the analysis is unlikely to have removed the risk of bias arising from the missing data.

D6: Bias in measurement of outcomes

Bias due to measurement of outcome was rated low due to the use of RDT for diagnostics

D7: Bias in selection of reported result

Risk of bias for selection of the reported result was rated as low for the prevalence outcome, as reported outcomes were the same as reported in the pilot implementation plan.

Uncontrolled before and after studies

The two uncontrolled before and after studies (**Ndong 2019**(21) and **Bharti 2020**(22)) were rated as critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design and therefore were not assessed further using a risk of bias tool.

Results by outcome

Effects reported on incidence of malaria infection at the community level

Incidence of malaria infection at the community level was reported by two cRCTs, **Desai 2020**(16) and **Larsen 2015**(18)at 0-12 months follow-up. **Desai 2020**(16) reported similar annual cumulative incidence of all malaria infection between intervention and control arms (crude IRR 0.95, 95% CI, 0.87-1.04). Similar results were reported by **Larsen 2015**(18) for incidence of malaria infection (IRR 0.83, 95% CI, 0.68-1.01). When effects were combined in meta-analysis, the pooled effect showed a small protective effect that was not statistically significant for effects of MTaT on incidence of malaria infection at the community level when compared to no intervention (RR 0.93, 95% CI, 0.86-1.01, **Figure 4**).

Figure 4. Effect of Mass Testing and Treatment vs no Mass Testing and Treatment on incidence of malaria infection at the community level

Two cRCTs reported incidence of malaria infection in children. **Sutanto 2018**(17) assessed incidence of malaria infection in two intervention arms (mass screening and treatment with two rounds and mass screening and treatment with three rounds) as compared to control arm. The risk ratio reported for mass screening and treatment-three rounds (MST3) and mass screening and treatment-two rounds (MST2) as compared to control arm (MST0) showed no significant difference in malaria infection among these groups (MST3 vs MST 0: RR 1.24, 95% CI, 0.31-4.97; MST 2 vs MST 0: RR 1.40, 95% CI, 0.33-5.96). Similarly, the RDT and microscopy-confirmed malaria episodes, reported in **Tiono 2013**(19), were not significantly different between the intervention and control arms (mean 1.69 vs 1.60, $p=0.3482$: RR 1.06, 95% CI, 0.12-9.21). When the data was pooled for meta-analysis, the effect did not show reduction in incidence of infection at community level (RR 1.27, 95% CI, 0.51-3.14, **Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Effect of Mass Testing and Treatment vs no Mass Testing and Treatment on incidence of malaria infection in children at the community level

Effects reported on prevalence of malaria infection at the community level

Samuels 2020 (15) reported prevalence of malaria infection annually for two years after three mass testing and treatment rounds. Cross-sectional surveys were conducted 2 months prior to first round of intervention and then 2 months after the completion of three rounds in year 1 and year 2. The effect size of intervention on prevalence was nonsignificant after year 1 (aRR⁹ 0.93, 95% CI, 0.0.80-1.09) and year 2 (aRR 0.92, 95% CI, 0.76-1.11). The pooled effect in meta-analysis showed a small protective but not statistically significant effect on prevalence of malaria infection at the community level in the intervention arms when compared to no intervention (RR 0.93, 95% CI, 0.82-1.04, **Figure 6**).

⁹ Data were analyzed with log binomial model using generalized estimating equations to account for clustering

Figure 6. Effect of Mass Testing and Treatment vs no Mass Testing and Treatment on prevalence of infection at the community level

Effects reported on incidence of clinical malaria at community level

Desai 2020(16) and **Larsen 2015**(18) reported incidence of clinical malaria 0-12 months follow-up collected monthly during the year. **Desai 2020**(16), reported 21% reduction in the incidence over the study period, however the reduction was not statistically significant (IRR 0.79, 95% CI, 0.61-1.02). On the other hand, **Larsen 2015**(18) reported significant reduction in malaria case incidence in the areas that received intervention (IRR 0.65, 95% CI, 0.54-0.78). When the effects were combined for meta-analysis, the pooled effect showed lower community-level incidence of clinical malaria (31% reduction) in the intervention arm than in the control arm (RR 0.69, 95% CI, 0.60-0.81, **Figure 7**).

Figure 7. Effect of Mass Testing and Treatment vs no Mass Testing and Treatment on incidence of clinical malaria at the community level

Effects reported on SAEs and AEs

Tiono 2013(19) reported SAEs monitored from the time of consent until 30 days after the subject stopped participation (time of last dose of treatment) and AEs during a period of 7 days from treatment administration. The study reported no significant differences in SAEs and AEs between the intervention and control arms. However, the data in the report did not specify SAEs and AEs separately for intervention and control arms, thus estimating effect size is not plausible.

Sutanto 2018(17) reported no SAEs, hence no withdrawals of subjects were observed due to AEs. Effect size was not calculable due to cumulative data of the most common AEs provided i.e., fever

(0.023/person-day), headache (0.008/person-day), vomiting (0.006/person-day), cough (0.004/person-day), shivering (0.003/person-day), and nasal congestion (0.002/person-day).

Effects reported on prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention

Prevalence of infection in the group targeted by the intervention was reported in three cRCTs. **Larson 2015**(18) reported prevalence of infection in children (1-59 months), 6 months post-intervention. The prevalence reported was lower in intervention areas i.e., MTaT significantly decreased the odds of malaria in the targeted population when compared to control (AOR¹⁰ 0.47, 95% CI, 0.24-0.90). **Sutanto 2018**(17), on the other hand reported prevalence of infection in two intervention arms comparing mass screening and treatment -three rounds (MST3) with mass screening and treatment -two rounds (MST2). The reported cluster level outcome did not provide total malaria prevalence, instead species-specific infections were reported. Cluster level MST3 vs MST2 analysis for *P. falciparum* (Pf) showed significantly lower-level Pf in MST3 (OR 0.25, 95% CI, 0.21-0.31), whereas there was no difference in MST3 vs MST2 for *P. vivax* (OR 0.87, 95% CI, 0.54-1.40). When combined, the effect size showed lower malaria prevalence in MST3 than in MST2 (OR 0.68, 95% CI, 0.5-0.93). **Tiono 2013**(19) reported prevalence of infection in asymptomatic carriers at 9 months post-intervention and there was no statistically significant difference found in prevalence of asymptomatic carriers in intervention and control arms (RR 0.9104, 95% CI, 0.8183-1.0129, p=0.0845).

All three non-randomized studies (NRS) also reported prevalence of infection in the group targeted by the intervention. The prevalence of symptomatic malaria reported by **Linn 2015**(20), a quasi-experimental study, at 21 weeks post-intervention found lower odds of symptomatic malaria in intervention arm than in control arm (AOR¹¹ 0.03, 95% CI, 0.02-0.07). **Ndong 2019**(21), on the other hand, in the uncontrolled before and after study reported prevalence of asymptomatic and symptomatic parasitemia. It was found that asymptomatic parasitemia between two time points (July 2017 & July 2018) was reduced odds of infection by 24% i.e., from 36.3% to 32.9% (AOR=0.76, 95% CI, 0.67-0.85, p=≤0.001), whereas there was only 9% reduction in symptomatic parasitemia over the period which was not significant (AOR 0.91, 95% CI, 0.67-1.38, p=0.672). The third NRS, **Bharti 2020**(22), was an uncontrolled before and after study, and did not implement mass surveillance and treatment (MSAT) in the same population over the time, instead all three rounds were in different transmission settings and prevalence was compared with the prevalence measured via passive surveillance in the region. In first round conducted in moderate to high annual parasitic area (API), prevalence from MSAT reported was 0.18% vs 0.06% from passive surveillance. The second round in low and high API areas showed 0.06% prevalence vs 0.03% prevalence via passive surveillance. The last round in low API areas around the cryptic cases only reported 0.03% prevalence measured through MSAT.

¹⁰ Fully adjusted for age, sex, household wealth, household ITN ownership, household IRS coverage, EVI and altitude.

¹¹ Adjusted for difference in population size, pre and post net coverage and SMC coverage.

Certainty of evidence

Incidence of malaria infection at the community level

For **Desai 2020**(16) and **Larsen 2015**(18), mass testing and treatment does not reduce incidence of malaria infection at the community level (high certainty of evidence but little to no effect size). **Sutanto 2018**(17) and **Tiono 2013**(19), study results revealed that mass testing and treatment likely results in little to no difference in incidence of malaria infection (moderate certainty of evidence but little to no effect size).

Prevalence of malaria infection at the community level

As reported by single study, (**Samuels 2020**(15)), mass testing and treatment does not reduce prevalence of infection at the community level (high certainty of evidence with little to no effect size).

Incidence of clinical malaria at the community level

As reported by **Desai 2020**(16) and **Larsen 2015**(18), mass testing and treatment reduces incidence of clinical malaria slightly in community (high certainty of evidence, Slight or some (public health value threshold)).

SAEs and AEs

For SAEs and AEs reported in **Tiono 2013**(19) and AEs reported in **Sutanto 2018**(17), the evidence was very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment on SAEs and AEs (very low certainty of evidence).

Prevalence of malaria infection among those targeted by the intervention

Three cRCTs reported prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention. For **Larsen 2015**(18), mass testing and treatment likely reduces prevalence of infection among those targeted (moderate certainty moderate effect size). As reported by the other cRCT, **Sutanto 2018**(17), an additional round of mass testing and treatment may result in large reduction in prevalence of infection (low certainty of evidence large effect size). The third cRCT, **Tiono 2013**(19) reported that mass testing and treatment likely does not reduces prevalence of infection (moderate certainty of evidence with little to no effect size).

One quasi-experimental study also reported prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention. As reported in **Linn 2015**(20), mass testing and treatment with screening for symptomatic malaria may reduce or have little to no effect on prevalence of infection in those targeted by the intervention, but the evidence is very uncertain (low certainty of evidence and moderate effect size). For the uncontrolled before and after study, **Ndong 2019**(21), the evidence was very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment on prevalence of symptomatic and asymptomatic parasitemia among those targeted by the intervention (very low certainty of evidence). For **Bharti 2020**(22), the evidence was very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment on prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention (very low certainty of evidence).

Acceptability

Acceptability of intervention was reported in two qualitative studies. **Shuford 2016**(23) qualitative study, linked to the impact of community-based mass testing and treatment in western Kenya reported in **Samuels 2020**(15), explored the perception of intermittent mass screening and treatment (iMSaT) in the community mostly in the absence of symptoms before and after the implementation. In the pre-implementation round, despite the willingness to participate and overall positive responses, there were concerns around testing in the absence of symptoms mostly due to the fear of covert HIV testing in those who were never tested with RDTs. There were mixed responses regarding perceived purpose and benefit of intervention. Only some participants understood the concept of asymptomatic malaria, whereas most of the participants verbalized concerns due to lack of understanding of asymptomatic malaria. As compared to testing, there were less concerns around treatment due to simpler dosing regimen except for affordability and accessibility of the drug once the trial is over. Other issues identified were failure to adherence, treatment effectiveness and need for intense sensitization activities. In the post-implementation round, although many participants appreciated the intervention and expressed overall positive experience, some concerns remained including fear of covert HIV testing and failure to treatment adherence.

The other qualitative study, **Silumbe 2015**(24) linked to population-wide mass testing and treatment in southern Zambia reported in **Larsen 2015**(18), aimed to understand the community health workers (CHWs) and community perception regarding mass testing and treatment. In general, mass testing and treatment was perceived very positively by most of the CHWs and community members. However, some barriers identified by CHWs were imperfect transportation to access hard-to-reach areas, difficulty in charging personal digital assistants (PDAs) for data collection due to unavailability of charging sources and commodity shortages. Likewise, in community participants, most barriers were related to perceived fear of covert HIV testing and use of blood samples for 'Satanism'. Lack of CHWs skills and training to conduct testing and treatment was also a perceived barrier among some community members. Lastly, this study also identified perceived feeling of wellness once symptoms subside as a barrier to adherence with treatment.

Resource Use

Data on resource use for mass testing and treatment was abstracted from one publication on cost and cost effectiveness (**Silumbe 2015**(25)) linked to the population-wide mass testing and treatment in southern Zambia as reported in **Larsen 2015**(18). The overall cost per RDT administered was \$4.39, whereas the overall cost for treatment with AL was \$34.74. Personnel and vehicles were the largest cost drivers, followed by trainings and RDTs. The estimated cost per disability adjusted life years (DALYs) averted was \$804, which in the context of Zambia was considered a highly cost-effective health intervention.

Feasibility

Data on feasibility and health system considerations were abstracted from two publications. **Odero 2019**(26), linked to impact of community-based mass testing and treatment in western Kenya reported in **Samuels 2020**(15), evaluated the feasibility of mass campaign at population level. It was emphasized that such a mass campaign requires well developed and maintained health and demographic system (HDSS) which if available makes such campaigns easier to implement. The study was conducted using highly trained research staff, which existed in this setting, however such challenges in resource limited settings can be overcome by implementing MTaT as a programme. Availability of health posts, community health

visitors (CHVs), available human resource at local health facilities and health management information systems all made this study feasible, eventually making MTaT more feasible as a malaria control program.

Ndong 2019(27), linked to the study conducted in Pakro sub-district (21) assessed the perception of health workers and community members about the feasibility of mass testing treatment and tracking (MTTT). Overall, the health workers and community participants perceived the MTTT as a feasible intervention with many benefits i.e., reducing incidence in children, increasing sensitization of community about malaria, reducing hospital admissions, and increasing work productivity, reducing expenditure for treatment, providing timely access to treatment at home, and reducing travels to health facility. With these benefits highlighted by the health workers and community, health workers showed concern about revenue lost. On the other hand, some of the challenges experienced during MTTT were misconceptions and rumors (fear of being infected with epilepsy by health workers), safety concerns from drugs and lack of trust in health workers (skills and knowledge).

Mathematical Modelling studies

Kern 2011(37): This study used a basic parasite model of malaria transmission in the human and mosquito population, which is a deterministic compartmental model. This study investigated the effect of community screening campaigns (CSC) and treating the asymptomatic *P. falciparum* carrier with artemether-lumefantrine (AL) on disease transmission. The simulation showed that areas with high endemicity with entomological inoculation rate of more than 200 had the largest effect, however the effects were not sustainable if the intervention were not repeated in subsequent year. On the other hand, areas with lower endemicity (EIR<10) showed sustained protective effect over three years with single intervention round.

Crowell 2013(36): This simulation study aimed to predict the incremental cost-effectiveness ratios (ICERs) of well-implemented mass screening and treatment in reducing the *P. falciparum* burden in SSA and comparing with the ICERs of scaling case management or ITNs, in absence of MSAT. Simulation model of dynamics of malaria biology and epidemiology was used with available literature on MSAT costs. In terms of reducing transmission, the authors found that MSAT was not cost-effective in low-transmission settings such as with EIR of two infectious bites per annum (IBPAPA). However, with EIR of 20 to 50 IBPAPA with 40% to 60% of ITNs coverage, ICER of MSAT was found similar to ICER of scaling up ITNs. Thus, it is a suitable intervention in moderate to high transmission setting and if considered for reducing malaria burden, it should be used as a complementary intervention.

Gerardin 2015(35): This study used data from nine study sites in an agent-based model of malaria transmission and immunity acquisition (EMOD DTK v1.6) to assess the effect of mass campaigns including mass screening and treatment (MSAT) for interrupting malaria transmission. In various simulations, the authors found that using MSAT in settings with recent reduction in EIR are more successful than in areas with no intervention and higher EIR. This is due to strong population immunity in recently reduced EIR areas compensating for ongoing transmission from low-density infections. However, simulations predicted that timing of such campaigns relative to ITN distribution is critical to drive the region towards elimination.

Slater 2015(33): This study used two established malaria models i.e., the imperial college model and OpenMalaria model (developed by the Swiss Tropical and Public Health Institute and the Liverpool School of Tropical medicine), to evaluate the impact of different diagnostic threshold on likelihood of MSAT success. These two models were applied to an African setting demonstrated that diagnostic threshold of 200 parasites microliter could interrupt transmission in the areas with EIR between 0.5 to 1.0 if intervention is continued for 8 consecutive years with high coverage. Increasing the diagnostic threshold by tenfold will interrupt transmission in the areas with EIR between 0.5-2.5 and by 100-fold with EIR between 2 and 4. So the African countries with EIR below 4 can benefit from this intervention if diagnostic test sensitivity detects 2 parasites per microliter. However, countries like Burkina Faso where EIR is more than 4, MSAT will not be an effective intervention even if diagnostic tests are highly sensitive.

Rosas-Aguirre 2015(34): Although this modelling study has evaluated focal screening and treatment (FSAT), the hotspots targeted through simulations are villages with delimited geographical boundaries. This modeling study used a deterministic model and assessed the long-term effects of FSAT on *P. falciparum* (Pf) malaria transmission in low endemic areas with passive case detection (PCD) in place with symptomatic case management. The model predicted that implementing FSAT with PCD reduced incidence and prevalence of Pf significantly. Three consecutive rounds of FSAT with PCR at the beginning of low transmission season predicted strongest reduction, whereas repeated rounds with PCR (5 years) or microscopy (10 years) would bring incidence and prevalence rates near zero.

Gerardin 2016(32): This study used data from southern Zambia in an agent-based model of malaria transmission and immunity acquisition (EMOD DTK v2.0) and compared various drug-based strategies ability to prevent clinical cases and interrupt transmission with minimal overtreatment of individuals those are not infected. The simulated model with MSAT predicted that even with increasing sensitivity of RDTs from 100 parasites microliter to 10 parasites microliter, low-density infection would remain, thus leaving substantial proportion of infection untreated.

Stuckey 2016(30): This modeling study evaluated effects of operational considerations of MTAT with different treatment modalities on health outcome using OpenMalaria model. The simulation predicted that with current available RDT, the low-density infection persists. Furthermore, changing drug did not result in reduction in mean parasite prevalence after one year of implementation.

Millar 2020(29): This study developed a spatial-explicit probabilistic model using publicly available data from six countries and estimated intervention cost considering different variables i.e., prevalence, diagnostic test performance and sociodemographic data including age and urbanicity. They concluded that resource allocation cannot be maximized with a “one-size-fits-all” approach due to substantial heterogeneity in malaria prevalence and performance of diagnostic test. This tool will help in calculating cost that is different from simplified cost analyses and will not undermine the cost associated with false-negative, delayed treatment and productivity lost cost during MSAT. This interactive tool developed will promote data-driven decision making by comparing the cost of MDA and MSAT.

Sallah 2020(28): This study used weekly malaria incidence from 45 villages in central Senegal and by using a metapopulation mathematical model, simulated different chemoprophylaxis interventions targeting hotspots. This model also incorporated human mobility with a differential-equation framework. The study

predicted that MSAT simulated intervention finally decrease incidence of malaria of more than 25% in low-transmission hotspot areas with five years of repeated intervention, whereas in high-transmission hotspot areas, five years of MSAT reduces around 57% of incidence.

Discussion

Summary of main results

In 2015, the WHO Malaria Policy Advisory Committee (MPAC) discouraged the use of mass screening and treatment (MSAT) due to absence of sufficient evidence on its ability to reduce malaria transmission. Since then, studies have been conducted in different transmission settings to evaluate the effect of mass testing and treatment (MTaT) on human malaria transmission. The purpose of this review was to systematically synthesize the available evidence on MTAAT and its effect on transmission.

This review included seven studies (eight reports): four cRCT, one quasi-experimental study and 2 uncontrolled before and after studies. Three cRCTs were conducted in moderate to high transmission endemicity settings, in western Kenya (**Samuels 2020(15)/Desai 2020(16)**), Burkina Faso (**Tiono 2013(19)**) and southern Zambia (**Larsen 2015(18)**), whereas the fourth cRCT (**Sutanto 2018(17)**) was conducted in a low transmission area of Indonesia. **Samuels 2020(15)/Desai 2020(16)** assessed the impact of three MTAAT rounds every four months annually over two years in villages as compared to standard of care. **Sutanto 2018(17)**, measured the effect of two intervention arms of mass screening and treatment (MST), i.e., with three rounds (MST3) monthly at five weeks interval and two rounds (MST2) with ten weeks interval within same time period, in villages and schools compared to no mass screening and treatment (MST0). ., The study evaluated the impact of an additional round of the intervention on the outcomes of interest. Larsen 2015(18) evaluated the outcome of three rounds of MTAAT over six months in districts and compared with contemporaneous control. Finally, **Tiono 2013(19)** implemented three rounds of MTAAT monthly before the start of the rainy season in villages and assessed the impact in comparison to standard of care. The quasi-experimental study (**Linn 2015(20)**) was conducted in rural Senegal where transmission is highly seasonal, and assessed the impact of district wide symptomatic screening, performing weekly ProACT sweeps for 21 weeks, and compared with the control arm (standard of care i.e., passive community case management). In the two uncontrolled before and after studies, **Ndong 2019(21)**, conducted in highly endemic area of eastern Ghana with continuous transmission, assessed the impact of four mass testing, treating and tracking (MTTT) rounds implemented every four months. The other before and after study, **Bharti 2020(22)**, assessed the impact of integrated vector control and surveillance activities including mass surveillance and treatment (MSAT) in varied annual parasitic incidence areas of Madhya Pradesh, India. However, the aim of MSAT in the latter study was to assess the difference in surveillance using MSAT as compared to the passive surveillance system.

Limited **randomized trials** contributed data to assess the effect of mass testing and treatment on outcomes of interest, and overall certainty of evidence was moderate to low. Furthermore, due to various

reasons like number of rounds, length of intervention, follow-up period, study design, varied transmission settings, etc., evaluating pooled impact was seldom possible. For incidence of malaria infection at the community level, pooled analyses from two trials does not reduce incidence of malaria infection at the community level, whereas pooled results from two other trials that used children as a surrogate for incidence of infection at the community level suggest that mass testing and treatment likely results in little to no difference in incidence of malaria infection at community level. Based on the results from a single trial, mass testing and treatment does not reduce prevalence of malaria infection at the community level. For incidence of clinical malaria at the community level, the pooled results from two trials suggest that mass testing and treatment reduces the incidence of clinical malaria slightly at the community level. It is worth noting that these studies were conducted in a population residing in moderate to high transmission areas, effect size despite of being significant requires greater absolute reduction in high burden areas to be considered of public health importance. For prevalence among those targeted by the intervention as an intermediate outcome on the way to reduction of community transmission, the trial conducted in a low transmission setting suggested that the intervention may result in large reduction in prevalence of infection among targeted group. The moderate transmission setting suggested that mass testing and treatment likely reduces prevalence among targeted group; and in the trial from the high transmission setting results suggested that mass testing and treatment likely does not reduce prevalence among targeted.

Incidence of malaria infection and incidence of clinical malaria at the community level were reported by two trials that were pooled for meta-analysis. It is worth mentioning here that the protective effect was evident for clinical malaria but not for malaria infection which may point to the diagnostic efficacy of confirmatory test vs the clinical judgement required for clinical confirmation of cases.

SAEs and AEs were assessed in two cRCTs (**Sutanto 2018**(17) and **Tiono 2013**(19)). In study reported by **Tiono 2013**(19), community-wide screening was conducted to identify asymptomatic *P. falciparum* carriers, whereas symptomatic treatment was provided irrespective of the study arm. The reported outcome in the study provides AEs and SAEs data that are only classified into AEs/SAEs in AL treated asymptomatic carrier and AL treated symptomatic episode, thus extracting data for intervention and control arm was not doable. Whereas **Sutanto 2018**(17) has reported common AEs without identifying either of the two intervention arms (MST3 or MST2), hence it is impossible to report if extra round had any effect on this outcome. For this outcome reported in both the studies, certainty of evidence was very low based on bias in reporting and imprecision, thus evidence was very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment on AEs including SAEs.

All three **non-randomized studies** (NRS) only reported prevalence of infection in the group targeted by the intervention. Based on the result from the quasi-experimental trial (**Linn 2015**(20)), although the effect size was moderate based on transmission setting, the certainty of evidence was very low due to risk of bias from not controlling for a potential bias and missing data; consequently, evidence was very uncertain about the effect of MTaT on prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention. Likewise, prevalence of symptomatic and asymptomatic malaria reported in the uncontrolled before and after study (**Ndong 2019**(21)), the evidence was very uncertain about the effect of mass testing and treatment on prevalence of symptomatic and asymptomatic parasitemia among those targeted by the

intervention (very low certainty of evidence). It is worth mentioning here that aOR showed a significant protective effect of 24% on asymptomatic parasitemia, whereas there was no effect recorded in symptomatic parasitemia. The reason could be that the intervention was more suitable to impact asymptomatic infections than clinical cases, which may have sufficiently been detected through surveillance based on health seeking behavior. Both NRS were pooled for prevalence of symptomatic malaria, but the heterogeneity was 98.8% indicating that these studies were not appropriate for meta-analysis. Given there were only two studies it was not possible to conduct any subsequent subgroup analyses. In contrary, **Bharti 2020** (22) did not assess the impact of MSAT on disease burden. The project-based study compared the prevalence measured through mass surveillance and treatment with the prevalence measured via passive surveillance, hence the evidence was very uncertain about the effect of MTaT on prevalence of infection among those targeted.

Three studies contributed data on contextual factors, highlighting the importance of community engagement before implementing campaigns like MTaT. Furthermore, ensuring adequate supply of commodities during such campaign is essential for effectiveness of any such intervention. Overall, MTaT was acceptable, feasible and cost-effective intervention.

The intent of an “accelerator strategy” is to reduce the human malaria transmission, by implementing a timely and effective intervention in a population, to the level where remaining cases are easily identifiable and can be eliminated with treatment. However, to reduce the transmission to this low level, it is critical to consider the asymptomatic cases or parasitemia while implementing any effective strategy. Mass testing and treatment is one such strategy that can reduce transmission to low level if screening instruments are sensitive enough to detect low level parasitemia. Most of the trials that were used to assess the new available evidence for this systematic review reported the limitation of diagnostic tools in detecting low levels of malaria parasites.

Overall, the certainty of evidence for outcomes in this review was based on a small number of included studies. Moreover, the range of outcomes reported in these trials varied, making it nearly impossible to pool the outcomes for meta-analysis. We excluded many studies because they did not meet the criteria for inclusion due to reasons including those where our outcomes of interest were not reported, or background interventions were not balanced across the arms. Albeit, these studies can provide useful information for policymakers.

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Other information

Registration and protocol

The review protocol has been registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO), registration number CRD42021259606.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Availability of data, code, and other materials

The review documents including data templates/forms and detailed data extracted from included studies are available by request and primary information on included studies available in MESA Track. Data analyses and code are not publicly available since they were conducted in a subscription-based software (Eppi-Reviewer).

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Characteristics of studies

Characteristics of included studies

Desai 2020 and Samuels 2020

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2013-2015
Location	Siaya district, western Kenya
Peak transmission season	May to July November to December
Baseline transmission intensity	High, baseline incidence rate 0.20 cases/p-y in intervention and 0.21 cases/p-y in control cluster parasite prevalence (median) was 33.9% in the intervention group and 36.8% in the control group
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i> , <i>Anopheles funestus</i> ,
Study design	Cluster-randomized controlled trial

Statistical power calculation	<p>Incidence- Assuming a baseline incidence of 1.6 infections per person per year, a type I error rate of 5%, and 80% power to detect a difference in malaria incidence between intervention and control arms of at least 30%. The study required 220 per arm each year and author adjusted the sample size to 330 per arm for an expected 18% loss.</p> <p>Prevalence- assuming a malaria infection prevalence of 40% in the control arm, a type I error rate of 5%, and 80% power to detect a relative difference in malaria prevalence of 50% between arms, 20 compounds per cluster were selected to attain calculated sample size</p>
Clusters	<p><u>Unit of randomization:</u> MTaT-wedges consisting of villages</p> <p>Incidence- Cohort of residents from 400 compounds Prevalence- 20 compounds from 20 clusters</p> <p><u>Features of the clusters:</u> Buffer areas, restricted randomization</p> <p><u>Number of clusters selected:</u> 30 <u>Number of clusters analyzed:</u> 20 <u>Average cluster size:</u> 10 villages</p>
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<p><u>Total:</u> all residents of 10 HF catchment area</p> <p><u>Intervention:</u> Incidence- Longitudinal cohort study: 330 participants Prevalence-Cross-sectional surveys: 20 compounds from the core area per cluster (857 participants)</p> <p><u>Comparison:</u> Incidence: Longitudinal cohort study: 330 participants Prevalence: Cross-sectional surveys: 20 compounds from the core area per cluster (857 participants)</p>
Participant characteristics	<p>MTaT: all inhabitants >1 month Longitudinal cohort studies: ≥ 1 year old Cross-sectional studies: ≥ 1 month old</p>
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Mass testing and treatment
Comparator	Standard of care
Background interventions	Long lasting insecticide nets (in both arms)
Drug and manufacturer	Dihydroartemisinin–piperaquine (DP; Duocotexcin, Holy-Cotec, China, or Eurartesim, Sigma-Tau, Italy); children aged 1-3 months treated with artemether–lumefantrine (AL); pregnant women with quinine
Dosage	40 mg dihydroartemisinin and 320 mg piperaquine for 6 years and above; 20mg dihydroartemisinin and 160mg for children > 3 months to 5 years
Number of rounds per season or year	3
Treatment interval	Every 4 months
Duration of the intervention	2 months

Treatment adherence	Round 1: 350/371 (94.34%), Round 2: 323/341 (94.72%), Round 3: 291/318 (91.51%), Round 4: 331/347 (95.39%), Round 5: 363/382 (95.03%), Round 6: 303/325 (93.23%)
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Incidence of malaria infection at the community level	<u>Measurement</u> : Longitudinal cohort, measured by microscopy/RDT <u>Timepoints</u> : 0-12 months <u>Sample size</u> : year 1: 516 (MTaT 253 & Control 263) year 2: 550 (MTaT 272 & Control 278)
Incidence of clinical malaria at the community level	<u>Measurement</u> : Passive surveillance, measured by RDT <u>Timepoints</u> : 0-12 months <u>Sample size</u> : N/A
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement</u> : Cross-sectional survey <u>Timepoints</u> : 2 months post intervention (third round of MTaT) <u>Sample size</u> : year 1: MTaT 179 (896 individuals) compounds & control 183 compounds (1016 individuals) year 2: MTaT 179 (841 individuals) compounds & control 190 compounds (907 individuals)

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Incidence of malaria infection at the community level</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	Used restricted randomization – “The communities within 3 km of each health facility were divided into three clusters of approximately equal population size. Two clusters around each health facility were randomly assigned to the control arm, and one to the intervention arm”
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“All villages whose midpoint was located within 3 km of each health facility were included in the study. The villages surrounding each health facility were divided into three clusters. One of the three clusters surrounding each health facility was randomly selected for the intervention, and the remaining two served as controls”.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters with baseline provided in Table 3 of Desai 2020
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	“All blood smears were independently read by two expert microscopists blinded to each other's results and to the participants' study arm”.

D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.
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Risk of bias

Outcome: Incidence of clinical malaria at the community level

Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	Used restricted randomization – “The communities within 3 km of each health facility were divided into three clusters of approximately equal population size. Two clusters around each health facility were randomly assigned to the control arm, and one to the intervention arm”
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“All villages whose midpoint was located within 3 km of each health facility were included in the study. The villages surrounding each health facility were divided into three clusters. One of the three clusters surrounding each health facility was randomly selected for the intervention, and the remaining two served as controls”.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	High risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters with baseline provided in Table 1 of Desai 2020
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	“All sick visits were recorded, including laboratory test results, presence and history of signs and symptoms, clinical diagnoses, and medications administered”.
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Risk of bias

Outcome: Prevalence of malaria infection at the community level

Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	Used restricted randomization – “The communities within 3 km of each health facility were divided into three clusters of approximately equal population size. Two clusters around each health facility were randomly assigned to the control arm, and one to the intervention arm”
D1b: Timing of identification or	Low risk	“All villages whose midpoint was located within 3 km of each health facility were included in the

recruitment of participants		study. The villages surrounding each health facility were divided into three clusters. One of the three clusters surrounding each health facility was randomly selected for the intervention, and the remaining two served as controls”.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters for every year with baseline provided in Table 1 and microscopy results in Table 2 of Samuels 2020
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	“All blood smears were read by 2 microscopists who were blinded to study arm; discordant reads were evaluated by a third blinded microscopist”
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Larsen 2015

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	Dec 2011-July 2013
Location	Gwembe, southern Kalomo, Siavonga, and Sinazongwe districts in southern Zambia
Peak transmission season	March-May
Baseline transmission intensity	Moderate, malaria parasite prevalence in children 1–59 months of age was 34.5% in the MTAT and 38.5% in control monthly confirmed case incidence in the preintervention period was 33.4 per 1,000 catchment population in control areas and 36.2 per 1,000 catchment population in intervention areas
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles arabiensis</i> and <i>Anopheles funestus</i>
Study design	Cluster randomized step-wedge control trial
Statistical power calculation	total sample size of 3,000 children < 5 years of age in 2,100 households > 2 rounds were sought to effectively measure a 50% reduction in malaria parasite prevalence between intervention and control groups, from an assumed 10% malaria parasite prevalence at baseline with a design effect of two.
Clusters	<u>Unit of randomization</u> : 46 HFCA, organized into 18 contiguous randomization group <u>Features of the clusters</u> : Satellite imagery from google earth <u>Number of clusters selected</u> : 18 <u>Number of clusters analyzed</u> : 18

Systematic Review on Mass Test and Treat

	Average cluster size: 2-3 HFCA
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>MTaT & Incidence</u> : All inhabitants of selected districts <u>Prevalence</u> : 3000 in 2100 households
Participant characteristics	<u>Prevalence</u> : children 1-59 months
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Mass testing and treatment
Comparator	Standard of care
Background interventions	ITNs and IRS
Drug and manufacturer	Artemether-lumefantrine (AL) as per recommendation by MOH
Dosage	As per national guidelines provided by MOH
Number of rounds per season or year	3
Treatment interval	Every other month
Duration of the intervention	1 year
Treatment adherence	No monitoring was done for treatment adherence
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Incidence of malaria infection at the community level	<u>Measurement</u> : HMIS based outpatient malaria confirmed cases <u>Timepoints</u> : 0-12 months <u>Sample Size</u> : All inhabitants of HFCA
Incidence of clinical malaria at the community level	<u>Measurement</u> : HMIS based outpatient malaria case incidence <u>Timepoints</u> : 0-12 months <u>Sample Size</u> : All inhabitants of HFCA
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement</u> : Malaria indicator household survey, by RDT <u>Timepoints</u> : 6 months post-intervention <u>Sample size</u> : 513 (intervention); 511 (control)

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Incidence of malaria infection at the community level</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	"The 46 HFCA's were organized into 18 contiguous randomization groups to be randomized to receive the MTAT intervention or serve as a control group. Each randomization group contained 2-3 HFCA's"
D1b: Timing of identification or	Low risk	"Satellite imagery from Google Earth was used to create the randomization groupings and then confirmed by District Health Teams".

recruitment of participants		
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters for every year with baseline provided in Table 6 of Larsen 2015
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	“Data for this outcome in intervention and control groups were obtained from the routine health management information system (HMIS) reported monthly by each health facility in the study area”.
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	All the study outcomes are provided in detail.

Risk of bias

Outcome: Incidence of clinical malaria at the community level

Domain	Author’s judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	“The 46 HFCAs were organized into 18 contiguous randomization groups to be randomized to receive the MTAT intervention or serve as a control group. Each randomization group contained 2–3 HFCAs”
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“Satellite imagery from Google Earth was used to create the randomization groupings and then confirmed by District Health Teams”.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters for every year with baseline provided in Table 6 of Larsen 2015
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	“Data for this outcome in intervention and control groups were obtained from the routine health management information system (HMIS) reported monthly by each health facility in the study area”.
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	All the study outcomes are provided in detail.

Risk of bias

Outcome: Prevalence of malaria infection among those targeted by the intervention

Domain	Author’s judgement	Justification
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D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	“The 46 HFCAs were organized into 18 contiguous randomization groups to be randomized to receive the MTAT intervention or serve as a control group. Each randomization group contained 2–3 HFCAs”
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“Satellite imagery from Google Earth was used to create the randomization groupings and then confirmed by District Health Teams”.
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters for every year with baseline provided in Table 1, 3, 4 & 5 of Larsen 2015
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	RDTs were used to detect malaria infection
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	All the study outcomes are provided in detail.

Sutanto 2018

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2013
Location	Wesiku district, West Timor, Indonesia
Peak transmission season	April-November
Baseline transmission intensity	Low, SPR in MST3 vs MST2 was 7.4% vs 8.7%
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum, Plasmodium vivax & Plasmodium malariae</i>
Vector species	<i>Anopheles barbirostris, Anopheles subpictus and Anopheles vagus</i>
Study design	open-label, community-wide cluster-randomized controlled trial
Statistical power calculation	The recruitment target was 1029 subjects per arm, considering a cluster design effect of 1.5, 5% significance, 80% power, and a 1:1 sample size ratio between intervention and control arms. A target of 115 children per arm would yield a power of 82% in detecting an estimated 50% reduction in malaria incidence following MST.
Clusters	<p><u>Unit of randomization</u>: Households</p> <p><u>Features of the clusters</u>: Stratified</p> <p><u>Number of clusters selected</u>: 16</p> <p><u>Number of clusters analyzed</u>: 11 for prevalence & 16 for incidence</p> <p><u>Average cluster size</u>: Average Households in clusters MST3-28, MST2-20, MST0-37</p>

Average Resident in clusters MST3-89, MST2-71, MST0-124	
PARTICIPANTS	
Targeted population	<u>Total:</u> All inhabitants for selected district <u>Intervention:</u> Prevalence 1029, Incidence 115 children <u>Comparison:</u> Prevalence 1029, Incidence 115 children
Participant characteristics	Prevalence: all inhabitants Incidence: school children
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Mass Testing and Treatment (MST)
Comparator	Standard of care
Background interventions	None
Drug and manufacturer	DHP (fixed-dose tablets of 40 mg dihydroartemisinin, 320 mg piperaquine; D-ARTEPP, Guilin Pharmaceutical Co, China, 6 December 2014 expiry); primaquine (15-mg primaquine base tablets; PT Phapros Tbk, Jakarta, Indonesia, October 2014 expiry)
Dosage	DHP regimen was daily based on patients' weight. For <i>P. falciparum</i> , primaquine was given as a single dose on day 1 as per patients' weight. For <i>P. vivax</i> infection the primaquine dose daily for 14 days as per patient weight
Number of rounds per season or year	MST3- 3 rounds MST2- 2 rounds
Treatment interval	MST3-5 weeks MST2-10 weeks
Duration of the intervention	6 months
Treatment adherence	Drug adherence was defined as taken completely as prescribed with witnessing, and occurred with >90% of cases
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Incidence of malaria infection at the community level	<u>Measurement:</u> Microscopy and PCR <u>Timepoints:</u> 0-6 months <u>Sample size:</u> 124 (MST3); 57 (MST2); 143 (MST0)
AEs	Drug administration during this study did not prompt withdrawal of any subject, and no serious AEs occurred. The most common AEs during treatment were fever (0.023/person-day), headache (0.008/person-day), vomiting (0.006/person-day), cough (0.004/person-day), shivering (0.003/person-day), and nasal congestion (0.002/person-day).
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement:</u> Microscopy and PCR <u>Timepoints:</u> 10 weeks <u>Sample size:</u> 530 (MST3); 345 (MST2)

Risk of bias

<i>Outcome: Incidence of malaria infection at the community level</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	Used stratified randomization – “households were assigned to clusters for random allocation to 1 of 3 treatments, that is, MST3:MST2: MST0”.
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“Households were geolocated and mapped using ArcGIS version 9.3 (Esri, Redlands, California). After excluding 129 households (for isolation, construction, or emptiness), 459 households were assigned to clusters”
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters in Table 2 of Sutanto 2018
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	Microscopy: “The first reading was performed in the field and the second reading (blinded to the first reading) in the central laboratory in Jakarta” PCR: “Real-Time PCR was performed in a in the Pharmacology laboratory of the Medical Faculty, University of Indonesia”.
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: AEs including SAEs</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	Used stratified randomization – “Clusters were randomized into either the intervention or control arm following a 1:1 ratio at a public draw involving the investigator, representatives from the sponsor, and the leaders from every cluster”.
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“All clusters considered for selection were part of a demographic surveillance system that routinely monitors the vital events occurring within these villages (e.g., births, deaths, in/out migration). All inhabitants of each cluster were invited to participate in the trial”
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	All slides were read by two independent microscopists

D5: Selection of the reported result	Some concerns	Cumulative data of all AEs has been provided
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Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	Used stratified randomization – “households were assigned to clusters for random allocation to 1 of 3 treatments, that is, MST3:MST2: MST0”.
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“Households were geolocated and mapped using ArcGIS version 9.3 (Esri, Redlands, California). After excluding 129 households (for isolation, construction, or emptiness), 459 households were assigned to clusters”
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	High risk	Data for this outcome are available, Figure 3 of Sutanto 2018
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	Microscopy: “The first reading was performed in the field and the second reading (blinded to the first reading) in the central laboratory in Jakarta” PCR: “Real-Time PCR was performed in a in the Pharmacology laboratory of the Medical Faculty, University of Indonesia”.
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Data for this outcome has not been provided for overall prevalence, instead species-specific data has been provided

Tiono 2013

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	January 2011 to January 2012
Location	Saponé district, Burkina Faso
Peak transmission season	June-November
Baseline transmission intensity	High, mean prevalence of asymptomatic carriers intervention 42.8% & control 47.5%
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Not mentioned</i>

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Study design	single-centre, controlled, parallel, cluster-randomized
Statistical power calculation	Not provided
Clusters	<u>Unit of randomization</u> : Villages <u>Features of the clusters</u> : Stratified randomization <u>Number of clusters selected</u> : 118 <u>Number of clusters analyzed</u> : 18 <u>Average cluster size</u> : 1 village
PARTICIPANTS	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : All inhabitants for selected district <u>Intervention</u> : 6817 <u>Comparison</u> : 7258
Participant characteristics	Prevalence: all inhabitants Incidence: children <5 years
INTERVENTION	
Intervention	Community-wide screening and treatment
Comparator	Standard of care
Background interventions	LLINs
Drug and manufacturer	AL/AL dispersible (20 mg artemether and 120 mg lumefantrine)
Dosage	twice a day for three consecutive days as per body weight
Number of rounds per season or year	3
Treatment interval	Every month
Duration of the intervention	1 year
Treatment adherence	Not quantified- AL adherence was good in those identified as asymptomatic carriers and in individuals with symptomatic malaria.
OUTCOMES	
Incidence of malaria infection at the community level	<u>Measurement</u> : Microscopy/RDT <u>Timepoints</u> : 0-12 months <u>Sample size</u> : intervention: 5897, control: 6510
AEs including SAEs	There were no notable differences in AEs or SAEs between the intervention arm and the control arm at either the cluster or individual level and no new or unexpected safety findings were recorded. In total, 0.3% of treated asymptomatic carriers reported at least one AE within 7 days of starting treatment.
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement</u> : Microscopy <u>Timepoints</u> : 9 months post-intervention <u>Sample size</u> : intervention: 5897, control: 6510

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Incidence of malaria infection at the community level</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	Used stratified randomization – “Clusters were randomized into either the intervention or control arm following a 1:1 ratio at a public draw involving the investigator, representatives from the sponsor, and the leaders from every cluster”.
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“All clusters considered for selection were part of a demographic surveillance system that routinely monitors the vital events occurring within these villages (e.g., births, deaths, in/out migration). All inhabitants of each cluster were invited to participate in the trial”
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	All slides were read by two independent microscopists
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov .

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: AEs including SAEs</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	Used stratified randomization – “Clusters were randomized into either the intervention or control arm following a 1:1 ratio at a public draw involving the investigator, representatives from the sponsor, and the leaders from every cluster”.
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“All clusters considered for selection were part of a demographic surveillance system that routinely monitors the vital events occurring within these villages (e.g., births, deaths, in/out migration). All inhabitants of each cluster were invited to participate in the trial”
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	All slides were read by two independent microscopists

D5: Selection of the reported result	Some concerns	Reported data has not been classified into intervention and control arms, but based on AEs and SAEs in treatment for symptomatic vs asymptomatic carrier
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Risk of bias

Outcome: Prevalence of infection among those targeted

Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1a: Randomization process	Low risk	Used stratified randomization – “Clusters were randomized into either the intervention or control arm following a 1:1 ratio at a public draw involving the investigator, representatives from the sponsor, and the leaders from every cluster”.
D1b: Timing of identification or recruitment of participants	Low risk	“All clusters considered for selection were part of a demographic surveillance system that routinely monitors the vital events occurring within these villages (e.g., births, deaths, in/out migration). All inhabitants of each cluster were invited to participate in the trial”
D2: Deviations from the intended interventions	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D3: Missing outcome data	Low risk	Data for this outcome are available for all the clusters
D4: Measurement of the outcome	Low risk	All slides were read by two independent microscopists
D5: Selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Linn 2015

Study characteristics

METHODS

Study dates	July to November 2013
Location	Saraya health district, South-east Senegal
Peak transmission season	July-November
Baseline transmission intensity	High, mean parasite prevalence of symptomatic malaria-intervention 1.88% and control 1.58%
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Not mentioned</i>
Study design	Quasi-experimental study design

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Statistical power calculation	Not applicable
Clusters	<u>N/A</u>
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 8954 <u>Intervention</u> : 4217 <u>Comparison</u> : 8954
Participant characteristics	All individuals of intervention households with symptoms of malaria
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	ProACT
Comparator	Passive community case management
Background interventions	LLINs & SMC
Drug and manufacturer	ACT
Dosage	As per national malaria control programme (NMCP)
Number of rounds per season or year	21
Treatment interval	Weekly
Duration of the intervention	21 weeks
Treatment adherence	Not mentioned
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<u>Measurement</u> : symptomatic screening with RDT <u>Timepoints</u> : 21 weeks <u>Sample size</u> : 3762

Risk of bias		
<i>Outcome: Prevalence of infection among those targeted</i>		
Domain	Author's judgement	Justification
D1: Bias due to confounding	Serious risk	Gold rush was one of the potential confounders and was not controlled for as a confounding factor in the analysis because data on gold mining were not systematically collected
D2: Bias due to selection of participants	Low risk	HCP performed weekly ProACT sweeps, going door to door to every household in the village, checking for individuals of all ages with symptoms of malaria

D3: Bias in classification of the intervention	Low risk	there was nothing to suggest that the intervention status was not well defined and classified.
D4: Deviations due to deviations from intended intervention	Low risk	Nothing to indicate that the intervention had any deviations from its intended format based on the trial context.
D5: Bias due to missing data	Moderate risk	Data register from one intervention health facility went missing
D6: Bias in measurement of outcome	Low risk	All slides were read by two independent microscopists
D7: Bias in selection of the reported result	Low risk	Reported primary and secondary outcomes are the same as reported on clinicaltrials.gov.

Ndong 2019

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2017-2018
Location	Pakro sub-district, Ghana
Peak transmission season	Perennial
Baseline transmission intensity	In July 2017, the prevalence of asymptomatic parasitemia was 36.3%
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>
Vector species	<i>Not mentioned</i>
Study design	Uncontrolled before and after
Statistical power calculation	Not applicable
Clusters	Not applicable
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 5000
Participant characteristics	All inhabitants of selected area
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Mass testing, treating and tracking (MTTT)

Comparator	Not applicable
Background interventions	Community case management
Drug and manufacturer	ACT
Dosage	As per the guidelines of National malaria control programme (NMCP)
Number of rounds per season or year	4
Treatment interval	4 months
Duration of the intervention	1 year
Treatment adherence	No data provided
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention (asymptomatic parasitemia)	<u>Measurement</u> : RDT <u>Timepoints</u> : Every four months at each round <u>Sample size</u> : Round 1: 3891 & Round 4: 4941
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention (symptomatic parasitemia)	<u>Measurement</u> : RDT <u>Timepoints</u> : 1 year

Risk of bias
<i>Outcome: All outcomes</i>
Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design

Bharti 2020

Study characteristics	
<i>METHODS</i>	
Study dates	2017 to 20020
Location	Mandla, Madhya Pradesh, India
Peak transmission season	June to September
Baseline transmission intensity	Varied with different annual parasitic incidence (API); Malaria prevalence 123 per 100,000
Parasite species	<i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>

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Vector species	<i>Not mentioned</i>
Study design	Uncontrolled before and after
Statistical power calculation	Not applicable
Clusters	Not applicable
<i>PARTICIPANTS</i>	
Targeted population	<u>Total</u> : 63,194
Participant characteristics	All inhabitants of selected area
<i>INTERVENTION</i>	
Intervention	Mass Screening and Treatment (MSAT)
Comparator	Not applicable
Background interventions	ITN, IRS, active case management
Drug and manufacturer	ACT
Dosage	As per the national drugs policy
Number of rounds per season or year	3
Treatment interval	-
Duration of the intervention	-
Treatment adherence	-
<i>OUTCOMES</i>	
Prevalence of infection among those targeted by the intervention	<p><u>Measurement</u>: RDT</p> <p>Three rounds of MTaT were conducted to determine prevalence in the asymptomatic reservoir. MTaT was compared with detection through passive surveillance prevalence. 1st round-moderate to high burden areas - 50/28,527 i.e. 0.18% vs 0.06% from passive surveillance; 2nd round-low to high burden areas - 7/11,363 i.e. 0.06% vs 0.03% from passive surveillance; 3rd round- RCD of cryptic cases in 50 households -3/8,467 i.e. 0.03%</p>

Risk of bias
<i>Outcome: All outcomes</i>
Critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design

Characteristics of excluded studies

Study	Reference	Reason for exclusion
Bal (2020)	(39)	Not retrieved

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Balogh (2014)		Not retrieved-Abstract presented in 63 rd Annual ASTMH meeting
Batwala (2011)	(40)	Intervention: febrile illness
Bennett (2019)	(41)	Not retrieved
Bousema (2013)	(42)	Crossed Referenced Article
Bousema (2016)	(43)	Excluded for Contextual Factors (Intervention: hotspot-targeted interventions with larviciding, distribution of long-lasting insecticide-treated nets, indoor residual spraying, and focal mass drug administration)
Briet (2017)		Not retrieved
Chaturvedi (2017)	(44)	Intervention: Mass screening to determine prevalence
Collins (2019)		
Conner (2020)	(45)	Intervention: combination strategies i.e. MTaT with PECADOM++ (weekly fever screening, testing and treatment)
Cook (2015)	(46)	Study focus area: testing RDTs vs PCR in MTaT
Crowell (2011)		Not retrieved
Crowell (2012)	(47)	Crossed Referenced Article-Primary article already included
Daniels (2020)	(48)	Outcomes: parasite relatedness and genomic diversity
Desai (2015)		Not retrieved
Dhiman (2011)	(49)	Intervention: fever screening/no assessment of impact of intervention
Diallo (2014)		Not retrieved
Diallo (2015)	(50)	Not retrieved
Faye (2015)		Not retrieved
Griffin (2010)	(51)	Excluded for Mathematical Modelling (Intervention: MTaT using single dose of ACT)
Griffin (2010)		Not retrieved
Grueninger (2011)		Not retrieved
Guelbeogo (2011)		Not retrieved
Hamainza (2014)	(52)	Population: Monthly household visit by CHWs for screening in healthfacility catchment area, not whole population residing in delimited area/ Excluded for Contextual Factors
Hamer (2020)	(53)	Crossed Referenced Article
Hennessee (2013)		Not retrieved
Kinzer (2010)	(54)	Study design: Only included those who tested negative in initial recruitment screening for follow-up in incidence study and treatment evaluation
Krishnamoorthy (1985)		Not retrieved
Landier (2018)	(55)	Intervention: testing febrile cases in community for early detection of cases
Larsen (2012)		Not retrieved
Larsen (2013)		Not retrieved/CRA

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Liew (2018)	(56)	Study design: RCD, followed with active case detection through test and treat post outbreak; no a study
Lover (2018)		Not retrieved
Lover (2019)	(57)	Not retrieved
Macauley (2005)	(58)	Study focus area: Case studies review
Maude (2009)	(59)	Excluded for Contextual Factors (Study focus area: commentary)
Mlacha (2020)	(60)	Intervention: This is a reactive strategy conducting MTaT based on weekly data from HF and only targeting villages with higher incidences in previous week
Minja (2019)		Not retrieved
Mosha (2013)	(61)	Intervention: Screen and treat approach vs tMDA/MDA
Mwanga (2015)	(62)	Excluded for Mathematical Modelling (Intervention: combination strategies that does not include MTaT)
Mwesigwa (2019)		Not retrieved
Mwesigwa (2019)	(63)	Excluded for Mathematical Modelling (Study focus area: evaluation of diagnostics)
Nankabirwa (2010)		Not retrieved
Nct (2016)	(64)	Not retrieved
Nikolov (2015)		Not retrieved
Pactr (2013)	(65)	Not retrieved
Pang (2001)	(66)	Excluded for Contextual Factors Intervention: symptoms based test and treat in target village)
Research (2017)	(67)	Crossed Referenced Article
Samuels (2014)	(68)	Not retrieved
Samuels (2015)		Not retrieved/CRA
Samuels (2017)	(69)	Crossed Referenced Article
Samuels (2020)		Crossed Referenced Article
Scott (2015)		Not retrieved
Scott (2016)	(70)	Study design: Cross sectional study determining the risk factors for malaria and RDT positivity
Shirayama (2008)	(71)	Study design: survey
Silal (2014)	(72)	Excluded for Mathematical Modelling (Intervention: MDA and FTaT)
Silal (2018)		Not retrieved
Silumbe (2012)		Not retrieved
Slater (2018)		Not retrieved
Stresman (2020)	(73)	Intervention: Reactive strategies
Stuckey (2014)		Not retrieved
Stuckey (2016)	(74)	Excluded for Mathematical Modelling(CRA)
Sutanto (2015)		Not retrieved
Sutcliffe (2012)	(75)	Study design: Longitudinal cohort & Cross sectional survey
Tairou (2015)		Not retrieved
Thanh (2015)	(76)	Intervention implementation criteria: Time frame does not include 1-24 months after the start of the intervention

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Tiono (2013)	(77)	Crossed Referenced Article
Tiono (2014)	(78)	Study focus area: evaluation of diagnostics
Villegas (2010)		Not retrieved
Vitor-Silva (2016)	(79)	Study design: prospective cohort
Wenger (2013)		Not retrieved
Wenger (2014)		Not retrieved

Characteristics of ongoing studies or recently completed studies

Study	Trial registration number	Reference	Comment
Collins (2019)	NCT 03705624	(80)	Recently completed-no results published yet
Hygiene (2019)	NCT04053907	(81)	Recently completed-no results published yet
Oxford (2018)	NCT04093765	(82)	Still recruiting
Research (2020)	NCT04301531	(83)	Still recruiting

Appendix 1. Search Strategy

Database: Ovid MEDLINE(R) and In-Process & Other Non-Indexed Citations <1946 to November 03, 2020>

Search Strategy:

-
- 1 *malaria/ or Antimalarials/
 - 2 exp malaria, falciparum/ or exp malaria, vivax/
 - 3 malaria ovale.mp. or Plasmodium ovale/
 - 4 plasmodium malariae.mp. or Plasmodium malariae/
 - 5 1 or 2 or 3 or 4
 - 6 "mass test and treat" or Mass testing and treatment ". tw or MTAT.tw
 - 7 mass screening.tw or Mass screening/
 - 8 (screening or screened or diagnosed or diagnostics or test*).adj2 mass
 - 9 ("case detection" or PACD or ACD).tw

10 "Population-wide" or "Community-wide" adj2 (test* or treat* or screen*)

11 "household screen*" .tw

12 "community case management" .tw or CCM .tw

13 "monthly screening and treatment" .tw or MSAT.tw

14 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13

15 5 and 14

Appendix 2. Selection process and data extraction (methods)

Figure i. Process Flow Diagram for Review Methodology

Process for including studies based on review question PICO criteria for synthesis and meta-analysis in parallel to systematic inclusion of contextual evidence that was integrated with results to support the guideline development panel in formulating final strategy recommendations.

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Figure ii. Adapted PRISMA Flow Diagram for Study Synthesis

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Table i. Variables for data extraction from included studies

Study design	Experimental	Cluster-randomized controlled trials Cluster-randomized crossover trials Cluster-randomized stepped wedge designs Cluster-randomized factorial designs Quasi-experimental cluster controlled trials Controlled before and after studies Interrupted time series (ITS) Uncontrolled before and after studies Before and after studies with historical controls
	Observational	Prospective Cohort Case-control Cross-sectional Qualitative
	Mathematical modelling studies	
Setting	Country	Region District Village
	Transmission	Season Endemicity Transmission intensity
	Location	Geographically delimited communities
Demographics	Population size	
	Population characteristics	Age Gender Other
Methodology	Testing	Diagnostic tools
	Treatment	Drug Dosage Treatment adherence Number of rounds per season/year Number of years of the intervention
Time period	Study period	Baseline length Intervention length Post intervention length
Infectious agent	Parasite species	
Baseline data	Pre-intervention measures	Incidence Prevalence
	Background interventions	Vector control Insecticide-treated nets Surveillance
	Coverage of background interventions	
Intervention	Intervention population coverage	Target Actual
	Intervention arms	
	Control arms	

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Outcomes	Community level	Incidence of malaria infection (parasitologically-confirmed malaria infection from a cohort study (active or passive detection of cases) Prevalence of malaria infection Elimination (defined as 0 indigenous or local cases for a period during the transmission season) Incidence of clinical malaria or number of indigenous malaria cases (febrile illness with parasitologically-confirmed malaria infection) Drug resistance markers
	Among the group targeted by the intervention	Adverse events Prevalence of infection Drug resistance markers
Other	Contextual study information	
	Potential study biases	
Partners	Study sponsors	
	Implementers	

Appendix 3. PRISMA Flow Diagram

*Reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched and the total number across all databases and registers.

**Some of the reports assessed for eligibility have also been assessed for contextual factors and/or modelling.

Adapted From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Reasons for exclusion

Incorrect intervention	Other strategies i.e. fMDA, MDA, reactive strategies, mass screening, etc.
	Combination of treatment tested
	Not the right treatment dose
Incorrect population	Not in Adults and children residing in a delimited geographic area
Incorrect study focus area	Study evaluates the efficacy of antimalarials, drug regimens/ dosing, diagnostic tests, supply chain, resource management, access to care, and/or quality of care and does not use the TDA intervention design
Background interventions	Imbalance of background interventions
Inappropriate comparison	Compared to another intervention without a control group
Incorrect study design	Does not meet study design criteria
Intervention implementation criteria	Time frame does not include 1-24 months after the start of the intervention

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	Follow-up periods for intervention and control groups are not the same
	Timing of baseline and endline surveys are not at the same time in intervention and control groups
	Length of pre-/ post-intervention periods for ITS studies are different (or cover different seasons)
Outcomes	Not the outcome of interest reported
Cross-referenced article	Supplementary article to a primary study already included/excluded
Ongoing study with no results available yet/report could not be retrieved	Ongoing study, report not retrieved
Abstract only/report could not be retrieved	Abstract, protocol or another document for which the full-text report could not be retrieved
Protocol only/report could not be retrieved	

PRISMA flow diagram for Systematic Review of Mass test and treat (MTaT) for reduction of human malaria transmission

*Reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched and the total number across all databases and registers).

**If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

Adapted From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

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